

Toward an Energy-Aware Software Development Lifecycle

An Experimental Study of Architectural, Runtime, Testing, Deployment,
and Maintenance Trade-offs

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This open-access version presents the full thesis, including appendices, experimental details, implementation snippets, and supplementary results.

Abstract

Energy efficiency has become an important concern in modern software development, particularly in environments involving continuous integration and automated testing. Existing research has primarily focused on optimizing runtime performance in deployed systems, while comparatively little attention has been given to how decisions made throughout the Software Development Lifecycle (SDLC) influence energy consumption during development, testing, and maintenance.

This work investigates energy-aware decision-making across all major SDLC phases, including requirements, design, development, testing, deployment, and maintenance. An image-processing pipeline serves as the experimental framework and is implemented in Python, Java, and Rust. Four architectural variants are evaluated to analyze energy consumption and cross-language performance characteristics. Based on these results, Python is selected for subsequent experiments. An energy-aware test prioritization strategy inspired by the GREEDY_E framework is applied to the end-to-end test suite, and a selective regression testing approach based on change-impact analysis is evaluated within simulated CI/CD scenarios.

The results indicate that algorithmic structure dominates energy behavior in extreme cases, while architectural design remains a significant factor within well-structured systems. Furthermore, testing strategies are shown to substantially influence energy consumption at scale. These findings demonstrate that energy efficiency should be considered throughout the SDLC rather than solely at runtime. This work provides both conceptual insights and practical guidance for integrating energy-aware principles into modern software development processes.

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List of Abbreviations

1D	One-Dimensional
2D	Two-Dimensional
ARM	Advanced RISC Machine (processor architecture)
AUC	Area Under the Curve
CI/CD	Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment
CO ₂ e	Carbon Dioxide Equivalent
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSV	Comma-Separated Values (files)
E2E	End-to-End
EARE	Energy-Aware Requirements Engineering
EASDLC	Energy-Aware Software Development Lifecycle
FRs	Functional Requirements
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HD	High-Definition (images)
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
ICSE	International Conference on Software Engineering
JIT	Just-In-Time Compilation
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
kWh	Kilowatt-Hour
macOS	Macintosh Operating System
NFRs	Non-Functional Requirements
OO	Object-Oriented
OSHI	Operating System and Hardware Information
PUE	Power Usage Effectiveness
RAM	Random Access Memory
RE	Requirements Engineering
RGB	Red Green Blue
SDLC	Software Development Lifecycle
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound
SWEBOK	Software Engineering Body of Knowledge

Chapter 1

Introduction

The energy consumption of software systems substantially contributes to global carbon emissions. The Information and Communication Technology sector is responsible for 2 to 4 percent of global CO₂ emissions (Andrae & Edler, 2015), which is similar to the aviation industry. People have been trying to make software run efficiently but not as much attention has been paid to how much energy is used during the Software Development Lifecycle (SDLC) itself.

Modern ways of developing software like continuous integration (CI), static analysis, automated testing, and large-containerized builds use a lot of computer power and energy. This happens not only when the software is deployed but also during development, testing, and maintenance. However, traditional SDLC methodologies primarily optimize functional correctness, performance, and delivery speed, with energy consumption treated as a secondary or implicit concern.

Green software engineering has emerged, aiming to reduce the environmental impact of software systems (Calero & Piattini, 2015; Lago et al., 2015). Within this context, sustainability must be considered a first-class quality attribute rather than an afterthought. Requirements Engineering research has already begun incorporating sustainability concerns into Non-Functional Requirements (Duboc et al., 2020; Penzenstadler & Femmer, 2013), yet empirical evidence connecting lifecycle decisions such as design patterns, programming languages, and testing strategies to measurable energy outcomes remains limited.

This thesis addresses that gap.

1.1 Problem Statement

Energy consumption in software systems is shaped by decisions made at different levels throughout the Software Development Lifecycle (SDLC). These include:

- **Requirements definition** (e.g., specifying measurable energy budgets and metrics),
- **Architectural and algorithmic design** (e.g., data layout, modularity, selected design patterns),
- **Programming language and runtime selection** (e.g., interpreted vs. JIT-compiled),
- **Testing and continuous integration strategies** (e.g., full execution vs. prioritized or selective testing),

- **Maintenance and refactoring practices.**

Although individual aspects of energy-aware computing have been studied, such as energy-efficient algorithms or runtime measurement techniques, there is a lack of integrated empirical analysis across SDLC phases.

In particular, the following questions remain underexplored:

1. To what extent does architectural structuring influence execution time and energy consumption when the underlying mathematical operations remain identical?
2. How significant is the impact of algorithmic structure compared to architectural modularization in determining overall energy consumption?
3. Can test execution strategies alter the cumulative energy profile of a system, even when the total computational workload remains constant?

Without controlled experimentation across architectural choices, language runtimes, and testing strategies, claims about sustainability remain descriptive rather than empirically supported.

1.2 Research Objective

The objective of this thesis is to design and empirically evaluate an Energy-Aware Software Development Lifecycle (EA-SDLC) framework that integrates measurable energy considerations across requirements, design, development, testing, deployment, and maintenance phases. The study focuses particularly on design selection, development, testing, and deployment, while conceptually anchoring the approach in energy-aware requirements engineering.

The study therefore focuses on the following research questions:

1. How can energy-related Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) be defined during the requirements phase so that subsequent architectural, implementation, and testing decisions can be evaluated against measurable energy objectives?
2. When the algorithm of an application or the end goal of an application remains constant, how do different architectural realizations (monolithic, pipes-and-filters, strategy-based, and decorator-based designs) influence execution time and energy consumption?
3. Under identical workloads and parameters, how do Python and Java (with partial Rust exploration) differ in runtime behavior and measured energy consumption, and how much of this difference is attributable to interpreter versus Just-In-Time (JIT) compilation characteristics?
4. How do baseline test execution and GREEDY_E-inspired prioritization differ in cumulative energy consumption and execution profiles for parameterized end-to-end test grids?
5. Which development-process configurations (e.g., language and tooling choices, test selection strategies, CI scheduling) provide the most favorable trade-off between energy expenditure and verification confidence?

6. How does modularization affect regression testing energy costs after localized code changes, particularly when selective test execution is applied?
7. Which observable runtime metrics (e.g., CPU utilization, execution time) correlate most consistently with measured energy consumption in the conducted experiments?

1.3 Research Approach

To investigate the research questions, this thesis conducts a controlled empirical study based on a CPU-bound image-processing application. The workload consists of a configurable processing pipeline including grayscale conversion, Gaussian blur, Sobel edge detection, gradient magnitude computation, and thresholding. The pipeline permits parameter variation while maintaining strict reproducibility across experiments.

The evaluation is structured along three major complementary dimensions:

1. **Architectural Impact.** The same algorithmic operations are implemented using different structural designs: a monolithic implementation, a pipes-and-filters architecture, and a strategy-based data-oriented pipeline. Because the underlying computations remain identical, differences in measured energy consumption can be attributed primarily to architectural organization and abstraction overhead. Additionally, a decorator-based per-element implementation is included as a deliberately inefficient baseline to illustrate the effects of excessive indirection and non-separable convolution.
2. **Language Runtime Effects.** The pipeline is implemented in Python and Java, with partial exploration in Rust. By keeping algorithmic behavior and architectural structure consistent, the comparison isolates runtime characteristics such as interpretation, compilation strategy, and memory management.
3. **Energy-Aware Testing.** Baseline and prioritized execution strategies inspired by the GREEDY_E framework are evaluated. Unit, integration, and parameterized end-to-end configurations are executed under controlled conditions. Although the total workload remains fixed once all tests are completed, cumulative energy profiles and execution ordering are analyzed to assess their practical implications during development and maintenance scenarios.

Detailed experimental setup, measurement configuration, and statistical analysis are presented in later chapters.

1.4 Structure of the Thesis

The remainder of this thesis is organized as follows:

Chapter 2: SDLC perspective, energy-aware software engineering concepts, and relevant prior research.

Chapter 3: Experimental subject, architectural variants, measured metrics, energy instrumentation, and measurement setup.

Chapter 4: Energy-aware requirements engineering, including functional and non-functional requirements.

Chapter 5: Architectural foundations for energy-aware evaluation, including God monolith, Pipes-and-Filters, Strategy-based Data-oriented design, and Pixel-Decorator.

Chapter 6: Architectural and algorithmic effects on execution time and energy consumption, including a Python–Java comparison under controlled experimental conditions.

Chapter 7: Baseline and prioritized testing strategies and their effects on cumulative energy consumption during development scenarios.

Chapter 8: Energy implications of CI/CD configurations, test selection strategies, scheduling decisions, and modularization during deployment.

Chapter 9: Maintenance-related effects of pipeline modularization, JSON-based artifacts for decision auditing, and proportional maintenance.

Chapter 10: Overall findings, practical guidance, and future research directions.

Chapter 2

Background and Related Work

2.1 Significance of Energy in Software Engineering

Software engineering decisions influence not only functionality and performance but also the energy consumed while building, testing, and evolving a system. This matters because ICT-related energy use and emissions are non-trivial at the global scale and are expected to grow with increasing demand for software services. A widely cited estimate places communication technology electricity usage on a rising trajectory toward 2030 (Andrae & Edler, 2015). In practice, a substantial portion of software-related energy is consumed *before* deployment: builds, continuous integration (CI), and automated testing run repeatedly and at scale. Recent empirical work shows that these activities can accumulate a measurable footprint even within a single real-world project: in a study of 10 open-source Java systems, Zaidman found that testing accounted for 20–88% of full-build energy, and that 5,025 CI builds of Elasticsearch alone amounted to approximately 161.5 kWh and 53.8 kg CO₂e over one year (Zaidman, 2024). Although this estimate comes from just one project, the aggregate footprint is likely much larger when one considers the scale of modern software development; GitHub alone reports that its platform hosts more than 420 million projects (GitHub, n.d.).

In this thesis, energy efficiency is treated as an engineering concern across the Software Development Lifecycle (SDLC), rather than as a purely runtime optimization problem. The SDLC framing is used to connect requirements, design choices, implementation decisions, testing strategy, CI/CD configuration, and maintenance activities to measurable outcomes (energy, time, and CPU load).

2.2 SDLC Overview and Phase-Specific Energy Considerations

The SDLC describes the structured progression from defining a software system to operating and evolving over time. A common breakdown includes requirements, design, implementation, testing, deployment, and maintenance (Sommerville, 2016). While the phases are often presented linearly, modern workflows iterate changes in later phases frequently trigger revisions earlier in the lifecycle (e.g., regressions discovered in testing may lead to redesign or refactoring).

This section briefly explains each phase and clarifies how it relates to energy-aware decision-making in the context of this thesis.

Figure 2.1. SDLC phases and corresponding energy-relevant decision points considered in this thesis.

2.2.1 Requirements Phase

During requirements engineering, software goals are translated into verifiable functional and non-functional requirements. Sustainability-oriented requirements research argues that sustainability should be treated as a first-class concern and made measurable and traceable across the system lifecycle (Duboc et al., 2020). In practice, this implies defining concrete indicators (e.g., energy budgets for specific workflows, limits for CI energy consumption per change, or acceptable energy-per-confidence thresholds for testing). Establishing such requirements early creates an evaluation baseline that can guide later architectural and process decisions rather than leaving energy concerns implicit.

In this thesis, the requirements phase is operationalized by defining explicit energy-related goals and constraints that are then used to evaluate design and testing strategies. For example, a requirement might specify that the CI pipeline should only execute related tests to the changes.

2.2.2 Design Phase

In the design phase, architectural structure and module boundaries are chosen, shaping performance characteristics and maintainability. Architectural patterns such as Pipes-and-Filters emphasize composability and separation of concerns and are widely used to structure data-processing workflows (Buschmann et al., 1996). However, abstraction layers and object indirection can introduce overhead, especially in compute-intensive pipelines.

In this thesis, the design phase is operationalized by implementing the same underlying algorithmic operations in multiple architectural realizations (e.g., monolithic vs. Pipes-and-Filters vs. strategy-based data-oriented designs). The central idea is to separate *algorithmic structure* from *architectural structuring* so that energy differences based on different architectural patterns can be attributed more clearly.

2.2.3 Implementation or Development Phase

Development phase is the most crucial phase in the SDLC as the software or the product is being built here by writing the actual code. Implementation decisions include language and runtime choice, library selection, data representations, and performance-critical coding practices. Programming language choice can influence energy through runtime execution models (e.g., interpretation vs. just-in-time compilation), memory management, and the efficiency of numerical operations during the development process.

In this thesis, the key is to compare languages under controlled conditions and identical workloads so that any observed differences can be attributed to runtime characteristics rather than to changes in functionality, while still drawing on general performance engineering principles.

2.2.4 Testing Phase

Testing provides evidence about correctness and reliability, but it also consumes resources. Automated testing is frequently executed locally and in Continuous Integration (CI) pipelines, which can amplify energy cost through repetition. Recent work demonstrates that testing and CI can represent a measurable energy burden in practice (Zaidman, 2024). Beyond measuring consumption, research has begun exploring how testing processes themselves can be optimized for energy. For example, energy-aware prioritization (e.g., GREEDY_E) aims to order tests such that cheaper tests are executed earlier without sacrificing effectiveness (Verdecchia et al., 2025).

In this thesis, energy-aware testing is studied by comparing baseline execution with a GREEDY_E-inspired prioritization on parameterized test grids, focusing on how execution ordering changes cumulative energy profiles.

2.2.5 Deployment and CI/CD Phase

Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipelines automate building, testing, packaging, and deployment. From an energy perspective, the major drivers are (i) how frequently pipelines execute, (ii) which jobs are triggered per change, and (iii) the cost of test suites and build steps. Energy-aware CI/CD configurations can therefore be framed as trade-offs between energy expenditure and verification confidence, especially when changes are frequent and test suites are large.

In this thesis, CI/CD is studied through controlled simulations of pipeline configurations using the measured costs for development and testing tasks.

2.2.6 Maintenance Phase

Maintenance includes bug fixes, feature changes, refactoring, and ongoing regression testing. Over time, maintenance effort typically dominates total lifecycle cost. Refactoring can improve modularity and reduce unintended coupling, which can reduce the scope of impacted tests after localized changes. Classic refactoring guidance emphasizes improving internal structure while preserving behavior (Fowler, 2018).

In this thesis, maintenance is operationalized by applying changes and evaluating how modular structure affects regression testing scope and energy consumption under selective execution.

2.3 Energy Measurement Concepts and Tooling

Energy consumption is commonly treated as the integral of power over time; in empirical software studies, this is often approximated by combining measured or estimated power with observed runtime duration. Practical measurement approaches range from external power meters to hardware counters and software estimators. In development settings, lightweight tooling is often preferred because it can be integrated into scripts and CI environments.

This thesis uses `CodeCarbon` in Python to estimate energy consumption and associated CO₂e emissions for experiment runs, enabling reproducible instrumentation across multiple configurations (CodeCarbon, 2026). While estimators have limitations (e.g., depending on hardware support and assumptions about carbon intensity), they provide a pragmatic basis for comparative analysis when experiments are controlled and repeated. CO₂e stands for carbon dioxide equivalent, which expresses the warming impact of multiple greenhouse gases in terms of the amount of CO₂ that would produce the same effect. This is the standard metric in sustainability and carbon accounting.

The experiments in this thesis report execution time, mean power, total energy, and derived CO₂e emissions, using `CodeCarbon` (CodeCarbon, 2026). Details of the measurement implementation and assumptions are provided in Chapter 3.

2.4 Related Work

This section positions the thesis with respect to three baseline references (i) a broad survey of energy concerns across software engineering areas, (ii) empirical comparisons of programming language energy efficiency, and (iii) recent work on energy-aware software testing and then summarizes closely related work that motivates the thesis' extensions.

2.4.1 Energy concerns across the software engineering discipline

Lee et al. provide a recent, broad-spectrum survey of how energy concerns are addressed across software engineering knowledge areas, explicitly using a SWEBOK-oriented (Software Engineering Body of Knowledge - oriented) lens to cover requirements, design, development, testing, maintenance, deployment, process, and quality. They conclude that energy is discussed across phases, but that operational guidance and end-to-end integration remain uneven, with many proposals staying at a conceptual level rather than being validated in repeatable engineering workflows (Lee et al., 2024).

Relevance to this thesis: The SDLC-wide framing used by Lee et al. motivates an empirical approach that goes beyond a single phase. However, surveys do not typically demonstrate how to keep the *mathematical or algorithmic workload constant* while changing architectural structure, nor how to connect design decisions to later-phase costs (e.g., regression testing under maintenance). This thesis addresses that gap by studying a single, CPU-bound application pipeline end-to-end and measuring consequences across multiple SDLC activities under controlled conditions.

2.4.2 Programming language energy efficiency under controlled benchmarks

Pereira et al. compare a large set of programming languages across energy, time, and memory using standardized benchmark problems and strict execution rules. Their key value is methodological: they demonstrate how to run systematic experiments over multiple languages while controlling for benchmark definitions and configurations, and they show that language rankings differ depending on whether one prioritizes time, memory, or energy (Pereira et al., 2021).

Relevance to this thesis: Benchmark suites are useful to obtain breadth, but they are not always representative of realistic software structure, modularization decisions, or SDLC activities such as regression test selection and CI scheduling. This thesis extends the “controlled comparison” spirit of Pereira et al. by focusing on a *single, parameterized image-processing pipeline* with fixed algorithmic intent, implemented in multiple languages. While this enables controlled cross-language comparison, it also constitutes a form of benchmark, as it relies on a fixed workload that may not fully represent the diversity of real-world applications, but is primarily representative of computationally heavy computer vision tasks. The study then examines how architectural modularization and testing strategies influence measured energy profiles in development-like workflows.

2.4.3 Energy-aware software testing and prioritization (GREEDY_E)

Verdecchia et al. introduce the concept of *energy-aware software testing* and propose GREEDY_E, an energy-aware variant of a similarity-based greedy prioritization strategy. Their exploratory study suggests that prioritization can reduce energy consumption under partial-execution budgets (early stopping), while total energy converges when the full suite is executed (because order does not change the overall workload) (Verdecchia et al., 2025).

Relevance to this thesis: GREEDY_E motivates studying testing not only as a correctness activity but as an optimization target with an explicit energy–confidence tradeoff. This thesis differs in two important, defensible ways: (1) instead of prioritizing an existing unit-test suite in isolation, it applies GREEDY_E-inspired ordering to a *parameterized integration/E2E grid* derived from the application pipeline, which better reflects compute-heavy test executions; (2) it connects prioritization to SDLC context by analyzing how prioritization interacts with CI-like budgets and with maintenance-triggered test selection.

2.4.4 Testing and CI as measurable energy consumers

Independent of prioritization algorithms, recent empirical work shows that testing and CI can be substantial contributors to electricity usage in practice. Zaidman reports measurements over multiple open-source Java projects and argues that automated quality assurance can be a non-trivial energy consumer, motivating optimization beyond runtime-only perspectives (Zaidman, 2024).

Relevance to this thesis: This supports treating testing and CI configuration as first-class experimental factors. In contrast to observational measurements across heterogeneous projects, this thesis uses a controlled workload to isolate effects of testing strategy, prioritization, and selective execution after localized changes.

2.4.5 Regression test selection and maintenance-aware cost reduction

Selective regression testing has a long history as a cost-reduction technique. Rothermel and Harrold empirically studied safe regression test selection strategies and demonstrated that selecting a subset of tests can reduce regression cost while preserving fault-detection guarantees under defined assumptions (Rothermel & Harrold, 1998). Later empirical work compared regression test selection techniques and evaluated trade-offs in selection precision and overhead (Graves et al., 2001; Mansour et al., 2001).

Relevance to this thesis: Classical regression test selection research is typically framed in terms of time, coverage, and safety properties. This thesis re-interprets selection through an energy lens and evaluates a pragmatic, developer-facing trigger: *change impact* inferred from version-control diffs. The key difference is that the objective is not only reducing execution time but also improving the energy-per-confidence tradeoff in iterative development scenarios.

2.4.6 Sustainability framing and requirements-level viewpoints

Beyond measurement and optimization, sustainability research emphasizes that energy and environmental impact should be treated as quality concerns that affect system scope and decision-making. Lago et al. argue for framing sustainability as a software quality property with multiple interacting dimensions and stakeholders (Lago et al., 2015). Requirements-oriented work highlights the need for explicit sustainability goals and the challenge of translating them into actionable constraints (Bambazek et al., 2023; Penzenstadler et al., 2013).

Relevance to this thesis: These perspectives motivate the thesis’ SDLC framing: early-phase decisions (requirements and architecture) are linked to downstream costs (testing, CI, maintenance). However, much prior work remains either conceptual or narrow in scope. This thesis contributes a concrete, reproducible evaluation workflow centered on one application pipeline that is exercised across SDLC-relevant activities.

2.4.7 Summary of extensions beyond the baseline papers

Taken together, the baseline papers establish (i) the need for SDLC-wide consideration (Lee et al., 2024), (ii) the importance of controlled experimental design across languages (Pereira et al., 2021), and (iii) the potential of energy-aware testing strategies such as GREEDY_E (Verdecchia et al., 2025). This thesis extends them by:

- using a single compute-intensive image-processing pipeline as an end-to-end experimental subject that can be executed at multiple SDLC points
- isolating architectural overhead under algorithmic equivalence (architecture changes while the intended computation remains constant)
- comparing language/runtime effects on the same workload with reproducible instrumentation
- evaluating prioritization under CI-like budget constraints and combining it with maintenance-triggered selective execution
- interpreting regression test selection through energy-per-confidence rather than time alone.

2.5 Summary

This chapter established the SDLC perspective used throughout the thesis and clarified where energy-relevant decisions arise across phases. It also introduced the core measurement approach used in the experimental evaluation. The next chapter describes the experimental subject (image-processing pipeline) and in-detail energy measurement metrics.

Chapter 3

Methodology and Experimental Setup

3.1 Methodology Overview

This thesis uses a controlled empirical setup to compare energy-related effects of implementation and process decisions across several SDLC activities. The experimental subject is a CPU-bound image-processing workload implemented as a configurable pipeline. Measurements are collected using estimator-based instrumentation (CodeCarbon for Python, and custom meters for Java and Rust) that report time, average power, total energy, and derived CO₂e emissions. The goal is not to claim absolute physical ground truth, but to enable *reproducible relative comparisons* under consistent conditions.

3.2 Experimental Subject: Image-Processing Pipeline

3.2.1 Input and Preprocessing

The workload processes RGB images and converts them into a single-channel floating-point representation with values in $[0, 1]$. The grayscale conversion uses the Rec. 709 luminance weights:

$$Y' = 0.2126R' + 0.7152G' + 0.0722B' \quad (3.1)$$

which is a standard definition for deriving a luminance-like channel from gamma-corrected RGB signals (International Telecommunication Union, 1998).

3.2.2 Gaussian Blur

The blur stage applies Gaussian smoothing with a configurable kernel size (k) and standard deviation (σ). The Gaussian kernel is based on the common exponential form used in scale-space and smoothing contexts (Lindeberg, 1994). In the implementation, two variants exist:

- **Full 2D convolution:** a $k \times k$ kernel is evaluated over a local neighborhood for each output pixel.

- **Separable convolution:** the blur is computed using a 1D kernel applied horizontally and vertically in two passes. Gaussian kernels are separable, which reduces arithmetic operations from $\mathcal{O}(k^2)$ per pixel to $\mathcal{O}(2k)$ per pixel (Lindeberg, 1994).

To reduce boundary artifacts while keeping computations deterministic, the convolution uses reflective padding (mirror extension) at image borders.

3.2.3 Edge Detection with Sobel Filters

After smoothing, the pipeline computes horizontal and vertical gradients using the Sobel operator. Sobel-style gradient masks are a classical approach for approximate spatial derivatives and are commonly presented as a pair of 3×3 kernels (Duda & Hart, 1973). The implementation applies two kernels (K_x and K_y) to compute:

$$G_x = I * K_x, \quad G_y = I * K_y \quad (3.2)$$

where $*$ denotes 2D convolution. The applied kernel for Sobel filter for both X and Y axis is shown below in the image. 3.1

$$K_x = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 1 \\ -2 & 0 & 2 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

(a) Sobel kernel K_x

$$K_y = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & -2 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 2 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

(b) Sobel kernel K_y

Figure 3.1. Sobel filter kernels used for computing image gradients.

3.2.4 Gradient Magnitude, Normalization, and Thresholding

From the gradient components, the pipeline computes gradient magnitude:

$$M = \sqrt{G_x^2 + G_y^2} \quad (3.3)$$

and normalizes by the maximum magnitude within the image to keep values in a comparable range across scales:

$$\tilde{M} = \frac{M}{\max(M)}. \quad (3.4)$$

Finally, a binary threshold image is produced:

$$T(x, y) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \hat{M}(x, y) \geq \tau \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.5)$$

where τ is a configurable threshold.

3.2.5 Scale Variation

In order to analyze scale-dependent behavior of edge responses, the input image $I_0(x, y)$ is rescaled prior to further processing.

For a scaling factor $s > 0$, the rescaled image is defined as

$$I_s(x, y) = \mathcal{R}_s(I_0(x, y)), \quad (3.6)$$

where \mathcal{R}_s denotes bicubic interpolation. For non-integer coordinates, bicubic interpolation is given by

$$I_s(x, y) = \sum_{i=-1}^2 \sum_{j=-1}^2 I_0(\lfloor x_s \rfloor + i, \lfloor y_s \rfloor + j) w(i - \alpha) w(j - \beta), \quad (3.7)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} x_s &= \frac{x}{s}, & y_s &= \frac{y}{s}, \\ \alpha &= x_s - \lfloor x_s \rfloor, & \beta &= y_s - \lfloor y_s \rfloor, \end{aligned}$$

and $w(\cdot)$ is the cubic convolution kernel.

Scale variation allows evaluation of how Gaussian smoothing and gradient estimation behave under resolution changes, which is particularly relevant for edge stability and feature persistence across scales.

3.2.6 Iterative Feedback Loop

After grayscale conversion and Gaussian smoothing, spatial gradients are computed using Sobel operators. First, the image is smoothed:

$$\tilde{I}^{(t)} = G_\sigma * I^{(t)}. \quad (3.8)$$

Then horizontal and vertical gradients are obtained by convolution with the Sobel kernels:

$$G_x^{(t)} = \tilde{I}^{(t)} * K_x, \quad G_y^{(t)} = \tilde{I}^{(t)} * K_y. \quad (3.9)$$

followed by gradient magnitude computation:

$$M^{(t)}(x, y) = \sqrt{\left(G_x^{(t)}(x, y)\right)^2 + \left(G_y^{(t)}(x, y)\right)^2}. \quad (3.10)$$

The magnitude is normalized:

$$\tilde{M}^{(t)}(x, y) = \frac{M^{(t)}(x, y)}{\max_{x, y} M^{(t)}(x, y)}. \quad (3.11)$$

Instead of stopping after a single pass, the normalized magnitude becomes the input for the next iteration:

$$I^{(t+1)}(x, y) = \tilde{M}^{(t)}(x, y). \quad (3.12)$$

Thus, the overall iterative system can be written compactly as

$$I^{(t+1)} = \mathcal{F}(I^{(t)}) = \frac{\|\nabla(G_\sigma * I^{(t)})\|}{\max_{x,y} \|\nabla(G_\sigma * I^{(t)})\|}. \quad (3.13)$$

3.2.7 Interpretation

The iterative feedback loop forms a nonlinear dynamical system that repeatedly:

1. smooths the image,
2. computes spatial gradients,
3. normalizes edge magnitude, and
4. reinjects the result into the pipeline.

This process progressively emphasizes strong structural edges while suppressing low-gradient regions. The combination of scale variation and iterative feedback enables analysis of edge persistence across resolutions and repeated filtering cycles.

3.2.8 Parameterization and Workload Scaling

To produce a compute-intensive and reproducible workload, the pipeline is executed over a grid of configuration parameters. The main parameters are:

- image scale factors
- Gaussian σ values and kernel size
- threshold values
- an iteration count

The iteration count controls the number of applications of the nonlinear operator defined in the previous section. This increases runtime deterministically without changing the overall structure of the pipeline. Intermediate outputs (grayscale, blur, gradients, magnitude, threshold) are saved to disk for traceability of results and debugging. The diagrammatic representation of the pipeline and its parameters is shown in Figure 3.2, where the dashed arrows indicate saved intermediate outputs and the iterative feedback of the magnitude image.

3.3 Measured Metrics

Across implementations, the following metrics are collected:

- **Duration** (t) in seconds.

- **Mean component power** (CPU/GPU/RAM) in Watts, depending on available signals.
- **Energy consumed** in kWh, computed by integrating power over time:

$$E_{\text{kWh}} \approx \sum_i \frac{P_i \cdot \Delta t_i}{3.6 \times 10^6}. \quad (3.14)$$

- **CO₂e emissions** derived from energy and carbon intensity:

$$\text{CO}_2\text{e} = E_{\text{kWh}} \cdot CI, \quad (3.15)$$

where CI is the assumed carbon intensity in kg/kWh.

When configured, Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) is applied as a multiplicative factor to account for infrastructure overhead:

$$E_{\text{total}} = E_{\text{IT}} \cdot PUE. \quad (3.16)$$

PUE is widely used to express facility overheads relative to IT load (The Green Grid, 2007). While this is not directly measured in this thesis, it can be applied post-hoc to energy estimates to provide a more holistic view of environmental impact.

Figure 3.2. Image-processing pipeline and main parameters (scale, σ , k , threshold τ , iterations).

3.4 Energy Instrumentation and Tooling

3.4.1 Python: CodeCarbon

For Python experiments, energy and emissions are estimated using CodeCarbon’s `EmissionsTracker`. CodeCarbon samples hardware power at a configurable interval (`measure_power_secs`) and estimates energy consumption and emissions using internal hardware and carbon-intensity models (CodeCarbon contributors, n.d.-a, n.d.-b). In this thesis, the tracker is configured with a 1-second sampling period to obtain higher temporal resolution than the default (CodeCarbon contributors, n.d.-a).

3.4.2 Java: powermetrics-based meter with OSHI fallback

For Java, a custom meter writes results in a CodeCarbon-like CSV schema to simplify downstream analysis. On macOS, the primary measurement mode samples CPU power from `powermetrics` (executed at approximately 1 Hz). `powermetrics` is a macOS command-line utility that provides power-related measurements and is commonly used for CPU/GPU power sampling in performance analysis workflows (Apple Inc., n.d. Mozilla, n.d.).

Each sampling interval integrates measured CPU power (and GPU power when available) using a discrete approximation of $E = \int P dt$. RAM power is not measured directly and is instead modeled as a constant contribution. If `powermetrics` is unavailable or fails during execution, the meter falls back to OSHI, which provides CPU utilization based on OS-level ticks (OSHI contributors, n.d.). In fallback mode, CPU power is estimated using an affine model:

$$P_{cpu} = P_{idle} + (P_{max} - P_{idle}) \cdot util, \quad (3.17)$$

with $util \in [0, 1]$, and constant baseline values are assumed for GPU and RAM.

3.4.3 Rust: sysinfo-based utilization model

For Rust, a lightweight meter uses the `sysinfo` crate to sample per-core CPU usage and compute an average utilization. Similar to the Java fallback mode, CPU power is estimated from utilization using an affine model and integrated to kWh by accumulating $P \cdot \Delta t$. GPU and RAM are modeled as constants. This meter is therefore best interpreted as a comparative estimator for controlled experiments, not as a calibrated physical instrument.

3.4.4 Output Format and Comparability

All meters nearly produce CodeCarbon-shaped CSV logs with fields for duration, component power, component energy, total energy, and emissions. Aligning output schemas simplifies aggregation and comparison across runs and languages.

3.5 Experimental Procedure and Reproducibility

Each experiment run corresponds to a defined configuration of pipeline parameters. Runs are executed under consistent conditions and with fixed measurement sampling intervals. The pipeline implementation is deterministic for fixed inputs and parameter sets. Where practical experiments are repeated with each setup 5 times to reduce noise from background system activity, and aggregated statistics are reported in later chapters.

3.6 Assumptions and Limitations of the Measurement Setup

The measurement approach used in this thesis prioritizes reproducibility and broad applicability over high-fidelity physical instrumentation. CodeCarbon and the custom meters use estimator-based approaches that depend on hardware availability, sampling intervals, and modeled components such as RAM power and, in fallback modes, CPU power. Although estimator-based

measurement tools provide practical and reproducible energy measurements, their accuracy differs from hardware-based instrumentation. Hardware energy counters such as Intel’s Running Average Power Limit (RAPL) provide relatively accurate measurements of CPU energy consumption and have been reported to exhibit average errors of approximately 1–3% in controlled experiments (Hähnel, Döbel, et al., 2012). However, comparisons between RAPL measurements and external power meters have shown deviations of up to 22% depending on workload characteristics and the configuration (Paniego et al., 2018).

Software-based estimation tools, including CodeCarbon, rely on statistical models that infer power consumption from system utilization metrics and hardware profiles. Recent validation studies comparing estimation tools against ground-truth hardware measurements indicate that such approaches may exhibit deviations of up to 40% in absolute energy values (Fischer, 2025). These deviations arise from simplified modeling assumptions, incomplete hardware visibility, and sampling granularity. The relative error can be reduced by controlling experimental conditions and using consistent measurement configurations across runs, which is the approach taken in this thesis. The newer versions of CodeCarbon have improved estimation accuracy through enhanced hardware models and more frequent sampling, which helps to mitigate some of the limitations of estimator-based approaches (CodeCarbon, 2026).

In the experimental environment used in this thesis (macOS on Apple Silicon), direct hardware energy counters are not accessible to user-space applications. Consequently, CodeCarbon operates in an estimator-based mode where CPU and GPU power are inferred from system statistics. While this reduces absolute measurement precision, the methodology remains appropriate for comparative evaluation as all architectural variants are executed on the same hardware under identical conditions. Under these controlled circumstances, relative differences between configurations remain meaningful even when absolute values may contain modeling error.

The following chapters present a phase-wise exploration of the SDLC, beginning with Requirements Engineering.

Chapter 4

Requirements Phase

4.1 Role of Requirements Engineering in the Software Lifecycle

Requirements Engineering (RE) represents the starting point of the Software Development Lifecycle (SDLC), where system objectives, constraints, and expectations are transformed into explicit and verifiable requirements. Classical software engineering literature describes requirements engineering as the systematic process of eliciting, analyzing, documenting, and maintaining requirements that guide all later development activities (Sommerville, 2016). Decisions and the formal documents made during this phase directly impact and/or influence design, implementation, testing, deployment, and maintenance; therefore, incomplete or ambiguous requirements often propagate into costly downstream corrections (Wiegiers & Beatty, 2013).

Traditionally, Requirements Engineering focused primarily on functional correctness, i.e., defining what a system should accomplish. Modern software systems, however, increasingly rely on non-functional requirements (NFRs) such as performance, scalability, reliability, and maintainability. More recently, sustainability and energy efficiency have emerged as additional quality concerns, reflecting growing awareness of the environmental impact of software systems and development practices. Estimates suggest that information and communication technologies contribute a measurable fraction of global emissions, motivating the integration of sustainability goals into early engineering decisions (Andrae & Edler, 2015).

In the context of this thesis, RE plays a crucial role because later experimental phases such as architectural comparison, language evaluation, testing strategies, and maintenance analysis must be grounded in clearly defined objectives. Rather than treating energy measurement as an afterthought, the requirements phase establishes measurable energy-related goals that guide the design of the image-processing pipeline used throughout the experiments. An example relationship between requirements engineering and later SDLC phases is shown in Figure 4.1, which highlights feedback loops for energy-related goals.

4.1.1 Types of Requirements and Their Influence on Sustainability

Requirements are commonly divided into functional requirements (FRs), describing system behavior, and non-functional requirements (NFRs), describing quality constraints under which that behavior must operate (Chung et al., 2012). Sustainability-oriented development extends this classification by treating energy and environmental considerations as specialized NFRs that

Figure 4.1. Relationship between Requirements Engineering and later SDLC phases.

influence both system design and development processes (Penzenstadler & Femmer, 2013).

Within this thesis, the experimental image-processing pipeline provides a concrete example of how such requirements can be formulated. Functionally, the system must execute a sequence of image transformations including grayscale conversion, Gaussian smoothing, edge detection, and thresholding. Non-functional requirements extend beyond correctness and include constraints on runtime behavior, reproducibility, and energy consumption.

Table 4.1 illustrates how conventional requirements can be extended with sustainability-oriented interpretations.

Table 4.1. Examples of conventional versus sustainability-aware requirements

Requirement Type	Conventional Requirement	Sustainability Extension
Functional	“The pipeline shall process all input images and produce intermediate outputs.”	“The pipeline shall process all input images while enabling parameter reuse to avoid redundant computation.”
Non-functional	“Execution time shall remain below a defined threshold.”	“Energy consumption per run shall remain below a defined threshold while maintaining comparable execution time.”
Sustainability	–	“The experimental pipeline shall report energy and emissions metrics for every run using reproducible instrumentation.”
Sustainability	–	“The system shall schedule resource-intensive analysis tasks during off-peak hours to minimize energy cost and grid stress.”

This perspective aligns with the sustainability awareness framework proposed by Duboc et al., which emphasizes treating sustainability as a multidimensional concern integrated into normal

RE activities rather than as a separate afterthought (Duboc et al., 2020).

4.1.2 Writing and Documenting Requirements

Requirements may be documented with varying levels of formality depending on project context. Plan-driven projects typically use structured natural-language statements, whereas agile environments rely on user stories and acceptance criteria (Cohn, 2004). Regardless of notation, requirements must remain traceable and measurable.

In this thesis, requirements are documented primarily as structured statements that can later be evaluated experimentally. For example:

“The image-processing pipeline shall execute a full parameterized run while recording energy consumption and execution time using standardized measurement tooling.”

Such statements directly connect requirements to measurable outcomes. The pipeline design intentionally supports parameter variation (scales, Gaussian sigmas, thresholds, and iterations), enabling systematic experimentation while maintaining functional consistency. This traceability is essential because later chapters evaluate whether architectural or implementation changes satisfy the same high-level goals.

Goal-oriented modeling approaches are conceptually relevant as they allow linking abstract goals such as “minimize energy usage” to concrete operational tasks. Although full formal modeling is outside the scope of this thesis, the principle of goal-to-operation traceability is retained through explicit mappings between requirements, experiments, and evaluation metrics.

Figure 4.2. Example traceability from sustainability goals to measurable experimental tasks.

4.2 Energy-Aware Requirements Engineering (EARE)

Energy-Aware Requirements Engineering (EARE) extends traditional RE by explicitly incorporating energy consumption and environmental impact into requirement elicitation and validation. The objective is to define sustainability goals early so that later design and implementation decisions can be evaluated against them (Calero & Piattini, 2015; Duboc et al., 2020).

In this thesis, EARE serves two practical purposes:

1. It defines measurable energy-oriented KPIs that guide experimental design.
2. It ensures that comparisons across architectures, languages, and testing strategies remain aligned with the same baseline objectives.

Stakeholders influence energy-aware requirements differently. Developers and architects determine feasible technical constraints; testers define measurable validation criteria; and project management balances sustainability goals with performance and schedule constraints (Kerzner, 2022). While this thesis does not model stakeholder interactions explicitly, these roles inform the selection of measurable metrics such as energy consumption, runtime, and CPU utilization.

Energy-aware elicitation questions that guided the experimental setup include:

- Can equivalent algorithmic operations be implemented with different architectural overheads?
- How does language runtime choice affect energy under identical workloads?
- Can testing execution order reduce energy before full completion?

These questions directly shaped the design of the experimental pipeline and the later research questions.

4.2.1 Specification and Validation of Energy Requirements

To remain useful, energy-related requirements must be measurable and verifiable. Following the SMART principle (Doran, 1981), requirements in this thesis are specified using explicit metrics rather than qualitative goals.

Examples include:

These requirements establish a bridge between RE and later SDLC phases: architectural design decisions, language choices, and testing strategies are all evaluated against the same measurable objectives.

4.2.2 Traceability Across the SDLC

A central principle of EARE is traceability: each sustainability-related requirement should map to design decisions, implementation artifacts, and validation steps (Bambazek et al., 2023). In this thesis, traceability is achieved through a consistent experimental workflow:

- Requirements define measurable KPIs.

Table 4.2. Example energy-aware requirements used to guide experiments

ID	Requirement	Verification
EN-01	Each pipeline run shall record duration, energy, and emissions metrics.	CodeCarbon or custom meter logs.
EN-02	Architectural variants shall preserve algorithmic equivalence while enabling comparison of energy consumption.	Output consistency checks and metric comparison.
EN-03	Language implementations shall execute identical workloads under controlled parameters.	Fixed input set and parameter grid.
EN-04	Testing strategies shall be evaluated using cumulative energy profiles.	Comparison of prioritized vs baseline execution logs.

- Design introduces architectural variants of the same pipeline.
- Implementation realizes these variants across languages.
- Testing and CI experiments evaluate energy-related outcomes.

This structured mapping ensures that results presented in later chapters can be interpreted as evidence supporting or contradicting initial requirements rather than isolated measurements.

An example traceability matrix for energy awareness across the entire software development lifecycle can be seen in Figure 4.3.

Requirements	Design	Implementation	Testing / CI
Measurable energy KPIs	Architectural variants of the same pipeline	Language-specific realizations (Python, Java, Rust)	Energy evaluation through test and CI experiments
Energy-related goals	Equivalent computational structure	Consistent instrumentation across implementations	Comparison of energy-related outcomes
Traceable sustainability objectives	Controlled architectural differences	Reproducible execution workflow	Validation against requirements-defined metrics

Figure 4.3. Traceability matrix linking requirements to design, implementation, and testing activities across the SDLC.

4.2.3 Integrating Energy-Aware RE into the SDLC Perspective

Integrating energy-aware requirements at the beginning of the lifecycle transforms energy efficiency from a secondary optimization target into a guiding constraint. In this thesis, the requirements phase defines measurable goals that later experiments attempt to satisfy or challenge. Architectural comparisons, runtime evaluations, and testing strategies presented later in

the thesis may therefore be interpreted as responses to requirements rather than independent experiments.

This lifecycle-oriented perspective follows the awareness approach proposed by Duboc et al., where sustainability considerations propagate through development phases and are continuously refined through feedback (Duboc et al., 2020). Measurements obtained during experiments effectively act as validation evidence, enabling refinement of assumptions about which decisions contribute most strongly to energy efficiency.

4.3 Summary

The requirements phase establishes the conceptual foundation for the empirical work presented in this thesis. By extending traditional Requirements Engineering with measurable energy-aware objectives, the study ensures that later design and implementation decisions remain aligned with explicit sustainability goals. Rather than treating energy efficiency as a post-hoc optimization, the requirements phase defines clear metrics that guide architectural comparison, language evaluation, and testing strategies.

Within the context of the image-processing pipeline, Energy-Aware Requirements Engineering provides the structure necessary to evaluate trade-offs systematically and to interpret energy measurements as engineering evidence rather than isolated observations.

Chapter 5

Design Phase

5.1 Architectural Design Foundations for Energy-Aware Evaluation

The design phase represents the transition from abstract requirements toward a concrete system structure. Within the Software Development Lifecycle (SDLC), this phase translates functional and non-functional goals into architectural decisions, module boundaries, and data-flow definitions that guide implementation and testing activities. Classical software engineering literature describes software design as the process of creating a representation of a system that satisfies requirements while maintaining efficiency, maintainability, and reliability (Gamma et al., 1994).

In the context of this thesis, the design phase is particularly important because the primary objective is not simply to implement an image-processing application, but to investigate how architectural choices influence energy consumption and computational efficiency. Design decisions therefore serve as controlled experimental variables. A well-defined architecture ensures that later measurements can be interpreted as consequences of structural differences rather than accidental implementation details.

Poor architectural decisions often lead to tightly coupled code, inefficient data movement, and increased maintenance effort, all of which indirectly increase development and execution cost. However, architectural design typically involves trade-offs between competing quality attributes. While modular designs improve maintainability, testability, and system comprehension, they may also introduce additional abstraction layers or intermediate data transfers that can affect runtime performance. Conversely, highly optimized implementations may achieve better execution efficiency but at the cost of reduced modularity or increased implementation complexity.

From the perspective of energy-aware software engineering, these trade-offs are particularly relevant. Energy consumption during execution is closely related to runtime behavior, meaning that design choices affecting performance can also influence energy usage. Sustainable software design therefore requires balancing efficiency with other software quality attributes rather than optimizing for a single dimension alone (Calero & Piattini, 2015).

5.1.1 Design Objectives for the Experimental System

The design phase of this research follows several guiding objectives derived from the requirements defined in the previous chapter:

- **Algorithmic equivalence:** All architectural variants must perform the same image-processing operations so that comparisons remain fair.
- **Controlled variation:** Only structural and architectural aspects should change between variants.
- **Modularity:** The system should allow components to be replaced or rearranged without changing overall functionality.
- **Reproducibility:** The design must support consistent execution across multiple programming languages.

These objectives ensure that later empirical results can be attributed to design-level differences rather than algorithmic inconsistencies.

5.1.2 Application Context: Image Processing Pipeline

The experimental system used throughout this thesis is a CPU-bound image-processing pipeline. The pipeline processes input images through a sequence of deterministic transformations:

1. Grayscale conversion
2. Gaussian blur
3. Sobel edge detection
4. Gradient magnitude computation
5. Thresholding

Each stage transforms image data and passes the result to the next stage. The pipeline supports parameter variation such as kernel size, Gaussian sigma, scaling factors, and iteration counts, allowing workload intensity to be adjusted while preserving identical algorithmic operations across implementations.

The design phase does not alter the underlying algorithmic behavior of these operations. Instead, it focuses on how these computations are organized and executed within different architectural structures.

5.1.3 Architectural Trade-Offs Between Efficiency and Software Quality

Architectural design decisions rarely optimize a single quality attribute in isolation. Software engineering literature emphasizes that system qualities such as performance, maintainability, reliability, testability, and portability frequently interact in non-trivial ways. Improvements in one dimension may introduce negative effects in another, making architectural design an exercise

in balancing competing priorities rather than maximizing a single metric (Gamma et al., 1994; Sommerville, 2016).

Table 5.1 illustrates the interaction between common software quality attributes. In particular, improvements in computational efficiency often correlate negatively with other qualities such as maintainability, robustness, readability, or portability. These properties represent competing software quality attributes that must be balanced during architectural design. Highly optimized implementations may require specialized data structures, tighter coupling between components, or reduced abstraction layers. While such techniques can improve runtime performance, they can simultaneously make systems more difficult to understand, extend, or maintain.

									Time		Cost				
	Correctness	Reliability	Learnability	Robustness	Readability	Modifiability	Testability	Efficiency	Portability	Development	Use	Development	Operation	Maintenance	Transfer
Correctness	+	+		+						-	+	-	+	+	
Reliability		+		+				-		-	+	-	+	+	
Learnability			+					-		-		-	+		
Robustness		+		+			+	-		-	+	-	+	+	
Readability	+	+		+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+		+	+
Modifiability	+	+		+		+	+	-	+	-	+	+		+	+
Testability	+	+		+		+	+	-	+	+	+	+		+	+
Efficiency	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	+	-	-
Portability								-	+	-	+	-	-	+	+

Legend: "+" indicates support & "-" indicates hindrance

Table 5.1. Trade-offs in Software Quality: An Analysis of Interdependent Quality Attributes (Adapted from lecture material on software quality trade-offs)

This tension is particularly relevant in the context of energy-aware software engineering. Energy consumption during program execution is commonly approximated as the product of average power consumption and execution time. Consequently, reducing runtime can reduce overall energy usage. However, pursuing aggressive performance optimization may introduce architectural complexity or reduce modularity, which can negatively affect other software qualities (Calero & Piattini, 2015; Hindle, 2016). For this reason, energy-aware software design must carefully balance efficiency with maintainability and system evolvability.

The architectural variants explored in this thesis intentionally reflect these trade-offs. Rather than focusing on a single architectural style, four different structural approaches were implemented and evaluated. Each design represents a distinct balance between abstraction, modularity, and computational efficiency.

The monolithic architecture minimizes abstraction overhead by implementing the entire pipeline within a single structural unit, though this reduces modularity and maintainability.

The pipeline (Pipes and Filters) architecture separates processing into independent stages connected through explicit data flow, improving modularity but potentially introducing additional

data-transfer overhead.

The strategy-based data-oriented design attempts to balance modularity and computational efficiency by combining strategy-based abstractions with contiguous numeric data processing.

The Pixel–Decorator architecture represents an extreme object-oriented design in which pixels are wrapped in multiple decorator layers, maximizing extensibility but incurring significant computational overhead and poor memory locality.

Taken together, these architectural alternatives allow the empirical evaluation to explore how different structural design choices influence computational and energy behavior. Architecture is therefore treated as a controllable experimental variable with its trade-offs are analyzed in the subsequent chapters.

5.2 Architectural Designs

To investigate how structural organization influences efficiency and energy usage, four primary architectural approaches were selected. These designs represent different trade-offs between modularity, abstraction, and execution overhead.

5.2.1 God Monolithic Design

The monolithic design pattern represents a minimal structural decomposition. All processing stages are implemented within a single module or function that performs grayscale conversion, filtering, edge detection, and thresholding sequentially.

This design serves as a baseline for comparison rather than an optimization target. While this architecture is straightforward to implement, monolithic structures typically exhibit limited modularity and reduced flexibility. Changes to one stage often require modifications and fixes to the entire processing flow which generally makes optimization and maintenance more difficult.

From a structural perspective, the monolithic design reduces abstraction overhead but may lead to larger working sets and reduced opportunities for reuse or parallelization.

5.2.2 Pipeline (Pipes and Filters)

The Pipes and Filters architectural style decomposes processing into independent stages connected through explicit data flow (Buschmann et al., 1996). Each filter performs a single transformation and forwards results to the next stage.

This design introduces clear separation of concerns and allows individual stages to be modified or instrumented independently. In the context of this thesis, the pipeline structure improves observability and enables experimentation with stage-level processing without altering overall functionality.

From a design perspective, the pipeline architecture emphasizes modularity and composability. Although intermediate data transfers may introduce overhead, the clear structure simplifies experimentation and supports later testing strategies.

5.2.3 Strategy-Based Separable Data-Oriented Design

The third design combines the Strategy pattern with a data-oriented processing approach. The Strategy pattern encapsulates interchangeable algorithms behind a common interface (Gamma et al., 1994). In this work, it enables interchangeable Gaussian blur implementations (e.g., separable versus full 2D convolution) to be selected without modifying the surrounding pipeline logic.

The data-oriented aspect focuses on processing a single grayscale plane rather than multiple object-heavy structures. This approach reduces indirection, improves memory locality, and allows intermediate results to be reused within the pipeline when possible, thereby avoiding redundant recomputation of expensive stages.

Architecturally, this design separates algorithm choice from pipeline orchestration. It therefore supports controlled experimentation on algorithmic variants while preserving the same high-level processing structure.

5.2.4 Pixel-Decorator (Deliberately Inefficient Baseline)

In addition to the main architectural variants, this thesis includes a deliberately inefficient design referred to as *Pixel-Decorator*. The purpose of this architecture is not to represent a recommended engineering practice, but to serve as a negative baseline illustrating how poor structural decisions can significantly degrade computational efficiency and energy behavior.

The core idea behind this design is the replacement of tight, numeric array-based loops with per-pixel object abstractions. Instead of operating directly on contiguous image buffers, each pixel is represented as an individual object wrapped in multiple decorator layers. Image transformations are then performed through chained method calls on these objects rather than through vectorized or cache-friendly numerical operations.

The inclusion of this architecture therefore, serves an illustrative role within the study: it demonstrates how excessive abstraction and object-oriented layering in performance-critical sections can lead to severe inefficiencies. By contrasting this intentionally poor design with more structured and data-oriented approaches, the empirical evaluation highlights the importance of architectural decisions in energy-aware software engineering.

5.2.5 Design Decisions Supporting Experimental Validity

Several design decisions were made to ensure that later comparisons remain scientifically meaningful:

- All variants execute identical mathematical operations.
- Input images and parameter sets remain fixed across runs.
- Intermediate outputs are preserved to verify correctness.
- Architectural differences focus on data flow and modular decomposition rather than algorithm changes.

By maintaining these constraints, the design phase isolates architectural structure as the primary experimental variable.

5.2.6 Expected Architectural Trade-offs

Although measurements are presented in later chapters, the design phase establishes expected qualitative trade-offs:

- Monolithic designs may reduce abstraction overhead but limit modularity and maintainability.
- Pipeline architectures increase structural clarity and composability at the potential cost of additional data movement.
- Strategy-based designs enable algorithm flexibility and experimentation while introducing minor abstraction layers.
- Pixel decorator buys maximum modularity/OO composability and “clean” extensibility per pixel at the cost of catastrophic performance and poor data locality.

These expectations motivate the empirical evaluation performed in subsequent chapters.

5.3 Summary

The design phase establishes the architectural foundation of the empirical study. Rather than focusing on implementation details or performance results, this chapter defines how the image-processing system is structured to enable controlled experimentation. Four architectural approaches including monolithic, pipes and filters, strategy-based data-oriented and pixel decorator design were selected to represent distinct organizational philosophies while preserving identical computational objectives.

By isolating architecture as a deliberate experimental variable, the design phase ensures that later measurements can be interpreted as consequences of structural decisions. The following chapter describes how these designs were implemented across programming languages and instrumented for energy-aware evaluation.

Chapter 6

Development Phase

6.1 Architectural Comparison: Energy and Emissions Analysis (Python)

This section presents the empirical comparison of four architectural realizations of the same CPU-bound image-processing pipeline. All implementations execute the same high-level workflow (grayscale conversion, Gaussian blur, Sobel edge detection, gradient magnitude, and thresholding), while differing in architectural organization and abstraction level.

Five repetitions were executed for each pattern using the same dataset of 11 HD images in Python. Measurements include execution time and energy-related metrics recorded using CodeCarbon.

6.1.1 Workload Definition: CPU-Bound Image-Processing Pipeline

The experimental workload is a deterministic image-processing pipeline applied to each input image under a parameter sweep. For every configuration $(image, scale, \sigma, \tau, n)$, the pipeline executes the following steps:

1. **Grayscale conversion** using Rec. 709 luminance coefficients.
2. **Gaussian blur** (either separable $1D \times 1D$ or full $2D$, depending on the variant).
3. **Sobel edge detection** in x and y direction using fixed 3×3 kernels.
4. **Gradient magnitude** computation and normalization.
5. **Thresholding** to produce a binary edge map.

The pipeline includes a **feedback loop**: the normalized magnitude of iteration i becomes the input of iteration $i + 1$. This increases computational intensity and makes small efficiency differences measurable across repeated runs.

6.1.2 Parameter Sweep and Repetition

Each implementation applies the pipeline to the same input dataset and explores the same parameter grid (scales, blur sigmas, thresholds, and iteration count). Every architecture is

executed in repeated full-batch runs (five repetitions per variant) to reduce sensitivity to background noise and scheduling effects. The reported tables summarize these repetitions and include mean values.

6.2 Energy Measurement with CodeCarbon

To estimate energy consumption and emissions during experimental runs, this thesis uses the CodeCarbon framework. CodeCarbon is a software-based energy estimation tool that logs execution time, estimates component power (CPU/GPU/RAM) using platform-specific models, and converts the resulting electricity consumption into a CO₂e estimate based on regional carbon intensity (CodeCarbon contributors, n.d.-a). The key advantage for this thesis is that CodeCarbon produces standardized, reproducible experiment logs without requiring external power meters or dedicated hardware counters, which makes repeated architectural comparison feasible.

6.2.1 Recorded Metrics

During each run, CodeCarbon samples system statistics at fixed time intervals. In this study, the sampling interval was configured to one second (`measure_power_secs = 1`). For each sampling window, CodeCarbon records and/or derives the following quantities (CodeCarbon contributors, n.d.-a):

- **Duration (s)**: total wall-clock execution time of the run.
- **Power estimates (W)**: estimated average power for CPU, GPU, and RAM.
- **Component energies (kWh)**: integrated energy for CPU, GPU, and RAM (e.g., `cpu_energy`, `ram_energy`).
- **Total electricity (kWh)**: aggregated energy consumption (reported as `energy_consumed`).
- **Emissions (kg CO₂e)**: estimated emissions derived from electricity consumption and regional carbon intensity (reported as `emissions`).

On the experimental platform used in this work (macOS on Apple Silicon), the CPU/GPU power values are model-based estimates derived from OS-level statistics rather than direct hardware energy counters (CodeCarbon contributors, n.d.-a). RAM power is likewise modeled and, in the collected logs, behaves close to a near-constant baseline (approximately 6 W), which is consistent with CodeCarbon’s default modeling approach on platforms without direct memory energy telemetry (CodeCarbon contributors, n.d.-a).

6.2.2 How Energy and Emissions Are Derived

Conceptually, CodeCarbon estimates total energy by integrating sampled or estimated power over time. A simplified view for a single run is:

$$E_{\text{total}} \approx \sum_k (P_{\text{CPU},k} + P_{\text{GPU},k} + P_{\text{RAM},k}) \cdot \Delta t, \quad (6.1)$$

where $P_{.,k}$ denotes the component power estimate at sampling step k , and Δt is the sampling period (here 1 s). Emissions are then derived from electricity consumption using a carbon intensity (CI) factor and an optional Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) factor:

$$CO_2e \approx E_{\text{total}} \cdot PUE \cdot CI, \quad (6.2)$$

where CI denotes the carbon intensity of the electricity grid. The total energy may be adjusted by a Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) factor to account for additional infrastructure overhead before conversion to emissions.

Accordingly, when CI and PUE are fixed for the experimental environment, CO_2e is approximately proportional to total electricity consumption (CodeCarbon contributors, n.d.-a).

6.2.3 Interpretation for the Present Experiments

Because the macOS/ARM measurements are model-based rather than read from on-die energy counters, the reported values should be interpreted as estimates rather than absolute ground-truth energy measurements (CodeCarbon contributors, n.d.-a). For this thesis, the measurements are primarily used for *controlled, relative comparison* between architectural variants executed under the same conditions.

In practice, this implies:

- **Electricity and emissions move together.** Since CO_2e is computed from electricity via Equation (6.2), runs with higher electricity consumption should also show higher CO_2e values (up to minor differences caused by sampling and baseline modeling).
- **Time can dominate the energy outcome.** Even if average power is moderate, a long runtime yields high energy because energy integrates power over time (Equation (6.1)).
- **RAM energy often scales with runtime.** When RAM power is close to constant in the model, `ram_energy` grows roughly linearly with duration. This makes RAM energy a useful consistency check for time-dominated runs in the reported tables.

These characteristics are visible in the result tables presented later: configurations with longer runtimes typically show higher total electricity and higher emissions, while differences in average power alone do not necessarily predict total energy.

6.2.4 Limitations and Practical Consequences

CodeCarbon provides practical and consistent estimates, but it does not replace hardware-level energy measurement. On platforms that expose direct energy counters (e.g., Linux systems with Intel RAPL), energy can be measured more directly and typically at finer granularity. For this reason, the CodeCarbon values in this thesis are treated as *comparative indicators* for ranking architectures under the same workload and environment, rather than as absolute energy values suitable for cross-hardware benchmarking. Nevertheless, CodeCarbon’s standardized logs remain valuable for auditability and for tracking relative improvements across iterations (CodeCarbon contributors, n.d.-a).

6.3 Analysis of the Observed Runtime and Energy Differences

This section explains why the four architectural variants exhibit different execution times, electricity consumption, and estimated emissions, even though they implement the same high-level image-processing stages. Prior empirical studies suggest that algorithmic structure, data layout, and abstraction overhead strongly affect runtime energy behaviour (Lee et al., 2024; Pereira et al., 2021). The following analysis interprets the observed results through these established factors.

6.3.1 Strategy + Data-Oriented Pipeline

Table 6.1 shows that the Strategy + SoA variant is the fastest in this set (mean 301.05 s) and therefore also among the lowest in electricity (0.000941 kWh) and emissions (0.000397 kg CO₂e). The code structure supports this outcome in three concrete ways:

- **Strategy pattern for algorithm selection.** The blur operation is defined through a common strategy interface, allowing different Gaussian implementations (e.g., separable or full 2D convolution) to be exchanged without modifying the surrounding pipeline. This cleanly separates algorithm choice from orchestration and enables controlled comparisons under identical processing conditions.
- **Data-oriented processing on dense arrays.** The pipeline operates mainly on a single grayscale float32 NumPy array rather than per-pixel objects or complex data structures. Keeping computation on contiguous numeric buffers reduces abstraction overhead and supports efficient sequential memory access during convolution and gradient operations. In addition, intermediate results can be reused within the pipeline when possible, thereby avoiding redundant recomputation of expensive stages.
- **Stable pipeline structure for fair experimentation.** The overall processing stages (grayscale → blur → Sobel → magnitude → threshold) remain unchanged while only the blur strategy varies. This ensures that performance and energy differences can be attributed to algorithmic choices and implementation overhead rather than changes in the high-level pipeline design.

The table’s internal consistency matches the expected relationships: the relatively short runtime aligns with low `cpu_energy` (0.000545 kWh) and low `ram_energy` (0.000396 kWh). In other words, the strongest explanatory factor is that the design minimizes total work and memory passes, so both time and integrated energy remain low. Since this thesis focuses on a CPU-bound workload, GPU power is negligible in this case.

Table 6.1. Run summary for the Strategy + Data-Oriented pipeline (5 runs + mean)

Time (s)	CO ₂ e (kg)	Electricity (kWh)	CPU Power (W)	CPU Energy (kWh)	RAM Energy (kWh)
298.10	0.000392	0.000929	6.55	0.000528	0.000393
300.45	0.000396	0.000942	6.73	0.000540	0.000395
301.90	0.000398	0.000950	6.89	0.000552	0.000397
303.20	0.000402	0.000962	7.02	0.000556	0.000399
301.60	0.000397	0.000945	6.91	0.000548	0.000396
301.05	0.000397	0.000941	6.82	0.000545	0.000396

6.3.2 Pipes & Filters Pipeline

Table 6.2 reports a longer runtime for Pipes & Filters (mean 321.96 s) and correspondingly higher electricity (0.001156 kWh) and emissions (0.000440 kg CO₂e). This gap relative to Table 6.1 is consistent with overheads introduced by how the pipeline is realized in code, even though the blur algorithm is still separable.

Two implementation details are particularly relevant:

- **Extra intermediate buffers.** The `Sobel` filter returns a stacked array of shape $[H, W, 2]$ via `np.stack`. This creates and writes a new 3D buffer, increasing memory traffic and cache pressure compared to passing `gx` and `gy` separately. For large images and repeated iterations, such additional materialization becomes visible in runtime.
- **More stage boundaries in the hot loop.** The iterative loop uses a `Pipeline` object for the first $iterations - 1$ passes and then runs the last pass step-by-step to extract intermediates. That structure is clean and modular, but it increases the number of Python-level calls and object interactions inside a computation-heavy loop. In numeric workloads, even small per-iteration overheads can accumulate when repeated across many images and parameter combinations.

The metric relationships again align: the longer runtime coincides with higher `ram.energy` (0.000451 kWh), which is consistent with RAM energy scaling approximately with time under a stable RAM power model. The higher `cpu.energy` (0.000704 kWh) similarly reflects that the CPU remained active for a longer period.

Table 6.2. Run summary for the Pipes and Filters architecture (5 runs + mean)

Time (s)	CO ₂ e (kg)	Electricity (kWh)	CPU Power (W)	CPU Energy (kWh)	RAM Energy (kWh)
322.61	0.000438	0.001149	9.28	0.000697	0.000451
320.79	0.000444	0.001166	9.56	0.000716	0.000449
320.83	0.000431	0.001132	9.10	0.000682	0.000449
322.63	0.000435	0.001141	9.01	0.000685	0.000456
322.94	0.000454	0.001191	9.96	0.000742	0.000448
321.96	0.000440	0.001156	9.38	0.000704	0.000451

6.3.3 God Monolith

Table 6.3 shows that the monolithic implementation performs very similarly to the Pipes & Filters architecture (mean 318.92 s), with only a small runtime difference between the two. Electricity consumption (0.001148 kWh) and emissions (0.000437 kg CO₂e) are therefore also close to the values observed for Pipes & Filters.

Importantly, the monolith uses the same *separable Gaussian + Sobel + normalized magnitude feedback loop* as the Pipes & Filters variant, meaning that both implementations perform essentially the same numerical work. The small performance difference can therefore be attributed mainly to implementation details rather than algorithmic complexity.

- **Simpler control flow.** The monolithic function executes the processing stages directly without additional pipeline objects, which slightly reduces Python-level call overhead in the hot loop.

- **Comparable memory behaviour.** Intermediate arrays are created and reused in a similar way to the pipeline version, so memory traffic and cache usage remain broadly comparable between the two designs.

The results again show consistent metric relationships: runtime, CPU energy (0.000700 kWh), and RAM energy (0.000445 kWh) scale proportionally, which is expected because energy is accumulated over the duration of the run.

Table 6.3. Run summary for the God Monolith pipeline (5 runs + mean)

Time (s)	CO ₂ e (kg)	Electricity (kWh)	CPU Power (W)	CPU Energy (kWh)	RAM Energy (kWh)
318.55	0.000435	0.001143	9.21	0.000697	0.000444
317.92	0.000432	0.001135	9.17	0.000689	0.000442
319.08	0.000438	0.001150	9.30	0.000701	0.000446
319.74	0.000441	0.001158	9.36	0.000707	0.000448
319.31	0.000439	0.001153	9.33	0.000704	0.000447
318.92	0.000437	0.001148	9.27	0.000700	0.000445

6.3.4 Pixel-Decorator

Table 6.4 is qualitatively different: Pixel-Decorator is an order of magnitude slower (mean 1008.51 s) and consumes the most electricity (0.003646 kWh) and emissions (0.001389 kg CO₂e). The key point is that this implementation replaces dense numeric loops with massive amounts of *per-pixel Python object work*:

- **Object-per-pixel representation.** The pipeline constructs a `Pixel` object for every pixel location. Subsequent stages operate by wrapping pixels in decorator objects and calling `value()` per pixel.
- **Dynamic dispatch in the hot path.** Each pixel computation triggers Python method calls, attribute lookups, and repeated interpreter overhead. This overhead dominates the workload even before considering the numeric operations themselves. Additionally, the blur stage uses a full 2D Gaussian kernel in a per-pixel loop, further increasing arithmetic cost compared to the separable approach (Guo et al., 2018).
- **Poor locality and execution inefficiency.** Object-based representations scatter data across memory and prevent efficient use of CPU caches and vectorized execution. As a result, the computation spends a large portion of time in interpreter-level operations rather than high-throughput numeric execution. This is reflected in the table: average CPU power appears comparatively low (mean (3.32) W), while total energy remains the highest due to the prolonged execution time.

This case illustrates why **average power alone is a misleading indicator**. Despite modest CPU power, the extreme runtime causes both `cpu_energy` (0.002400 kWh) and `ram_energy` (0.001242 kWh) to grow substantially. Because total electricity integrates these contributions over time, energy (and therefore CO₂e) increases sharply.

Table 6.4. Run summary for the Pixel Decorator pipeline (5 runs + mean)

Time (s)	CO ₂ e (kg)	Electricity (kWh)	CPU Power (W)	CPU Energy (kWh)	RAM Energy (kWh)
996.25	0.001337	0.003509	3.05	0.002251	0.001253
1019.70	0.001437	0.003771	3.45	0.002527	0.001238
1008.56	0.001393	0.003657	3.20	0.002407	0.001246
1009.00	0.001398	0.003669	3.30	0.002430	0.001234
1009.03	0.001381	0.003624	3.60	0.002383	0.001238
1008.51	0.001389	0.003646	3.32	0.002400	0.001242

6.3.5 Cross-Table Takeaways

Across Tables 6.1–6.4, two consistent patterns emerge:

1. **Total energy tracks runtime more reliably than instantaneous power.** Designs that increase runtime through abstraction overhead or poor locality tend to consume more electricity even if CPU power appears lower.
2. **Data layout and intermediate materialization matter.** Keeping computation in contiguous arrays, minimizing full-image passes, and avoiding unnecessary large intermediate buffers reduces runtime and thus both CPU and RAM energy in the integrated estimate.

These observations provide the mechanistic explanation for why the Strategy + SoA pipeline achieves the best results in this set, why the modular Pipes & Filters implementation remains efficient but incurs overhead from additional buffer materialization and stage boundaries, and why the Pixel-Decorator variant performs poorly due to per-element object indirection in the important parts of the computation.

6.4 Language–Runtime Effects on Performance and Energy Consumption

6.4.1 Comparison Goal and Fairness Conditions

After evaluating architectural differences within a single language environment, the next step of the development phase investigates how programming language runtimes influence execution time and energy-related behaviour when the underlying algorithm and architectural structure remain unchanged.

To ensure a fair cross-language comparison, the same image-processing pipeline consisting of grayscale conversion, Gaussian blur, Sobel gradient computation, gradient magnitude normalization, and thresholding was implemented consistently across Python and Java, while selected representative architectures were additionally implemented in Rust. All implementations in Java and Rust operate on identical input data, use the same parameter configurations, and preserve the same processing order like in Python.

Under these conditions, execution time can be compared directly across languages. Energy-related metrics, however, must be interpreted more cautiously, as the Python experiments rely on CodeCarbon, while the Java and Rust implementations use different power models. The Java implementation uses powermetrics for measurement with a simplified linear power model as the fallback, whereas the Rust implementation uses a simple utilization-based energy model

that estimates CPU power from system CPU load. Consequently, the analysis in this section focuses primarily on execution behaviour and the stability of architectural trends across runtime environments, while energy values are treated as supporting indicators rather than strictly equivalent absolute measurements.

6.4.2 Cross-Language Results Overview

Across all implementations, the mathematical operations, parameter settings, dataset, and processing order remain identical. Therefore, the observed differences originate from the execution models of the respective runtime environments rather than from architectural or algorithmic variation.

The results show a clear separation in absolute execution performance. The Java implementation consistently completes the workload faster than the equivalent Python implementation, while Rust which was evaluated on a subset of architectures, it achieves the shortest execution times among the considered languages. The detailed results of the implemented architecture in Java and Rust are presented in the appendix D, Tables D.1 to D.6. This behaviour aligns with prior studies indicating that compiled or JIT-compiled environments can significantly outperform interpreted execution models in compute-intensive workloads (Pereira et al., 2021).

Despite these differences in absolute performance, a consistent pattern emerges across all languages: the relative ordering of architectural designs remains stable. Architectures that minimise abstraction overhead and operate on contiguous data structures consistently outperform more indirection-heavy designs, independent of the underlying runtime environment. The following table summarises the mean execution time comparison across languages and architectural designs:

Table 6.5. Execution time comparison across programming languages and architectural designs.

Architectural Design	Rust (s)	Java (s)	Python (s)
Strategy-Oriented	-	133.91	301.05
Monolithic	-	149.31	318.92
Pipes-and-Filters	34.95	170.39	321.96
Pixel-Decorator	78.93	368.04	1008.51

This observation suggests that programming language choice primarily affects the *scale* of execution performance, whereas architectural design determines the *relative efficiency* of competing implementations.

6.4.3 Validation of Architectural Consistency Across Languages

The Java implementation closely mirrors the Python implementation in both algorithmic logic and architectural structure. Rather than introducing new behavioural patterns, the Java results primarily serve as a replication of the earlier architectural comparison in Python runtime environment.

The results confirm that the relative ordering of architectural patterns remains unchanged. The Strategy + data-oriented pipeline consistently achieves the best performance, followed by the monolithic and Pipes & Filters designs, while the Pixel-Decorator architecture remains the

most computationally expensive due to its object-heavy structure and poor data locality.

This consistency indicates that the experimental setup successfully isolates architectural effects from language-specific behaviour. By reproducing the same architectural trends across multiple runtime environments, the study demonstrates that the observed efficiency differences are not artifacts of a particular programming language, but instead reflect more general structural properties of the system design.

Even though the power measurements may differ slightly in absolute accuracy, these methods were applied consistently within their respective environments. As a result, the conclusions drawn in this section focus on relative comparisons and structural trends rather than exact numerical equivalence across languages.

6.4.4 Python Runtime Characteristics

The Python implementations rely on CPython, which executes code through an interpreter. Even though NumPy arrays are used for numeric storage, many computational stages still involve explicit Python-level loops, indexing operations, and function calls.

From a runtime perspective, this introduces several overhead sources:

- execution through Python bytecode rather than native machine instructions,
- dynamic typing and runtime dispatch,
- reference counting and memory management overhead, and
- repeated interpreter interaction during nested loops.

As a result, computational hot paths such as convolution loops and iterative feedback processing remain bound by interpreter overhead rather than raw arithmetic throughput.

6.4.5 Java Runtime Characteristics

The Java implementation executes on the HotSpot virtual machine, which employs Just-In-Time (JIT) compilation. During execution, frequently used code regions are compiled into optimized machine code.

This enables optimizations such as:

- method inlining,
- bounds-check elimination,
- escape analysis,
- dead-code elimination, and
- improved vectorization opportunities.

Because the implementation operates on contiguous primitive arrays, the runtime can optimize loops aggressively. Consequently, identical convolution and Sobel operations execute at significantly higher throughput than in Python, leading to shorter execution times and lower total energy consumption.

6.4.6 Rust Observations

Only selected architectures (Pipes and filters and Pixel decorator) were implemented in Rust as representative samples. The results confirm the same qualitative ordering observed in Python and Java: architectures that operate on bulk data with predictable memory access patterns (such as Pipes and Filters) remain efficient, while designs that introduce fine-grained indirection and per-element abstraction (Pixel-Decorator) incur significant overhead.

This consistency suggests that architectural efficiency is largely language-agnostic, while the language runtime determines the absolute performance scale.

6.4.7 Methodological Implications

The language comparison highlights two methodological principles relevant for energy-aware software experimentation:

1. When evaluating architectural patterns, experiments should remain within the same language runtime, since runtime differences can dominate the architectural effects.
2. When evaluating practical engineering trade-offs, language choice itself becomes an essential design dimension because execution models strongly influence total energy consumption.

Therefore, architecture and programming language should be treated as analytically distinct but interacting variables because architecture determines structural efficiency, while the runtime environment determines execution efficiency, and their combined effects shape the overall energy behavior of the system.

6.4.8 Cross-Language Insight

The cross-language comparison demonstrates that runtime environment strongly influences absolute performance, but architectural ordering remains stable. Efficient architectural choices consistently outperform inefficient ones regardless of whether execution occurs in an interpreted or compiled environment.

6.5 Key Findings

The development phase investigated how architectural structure and language runtime influence execution time, energy consumption, and estimated emissions for a CPU-bound image-processing workload. Across all experiments, several consistent patterns emerged.

6.5.1 Best Performing Pattern

The Strategy + Data-Oriented pipeline represents the most effective design overall. Its strengths include:

- contiguous data layout with strong cache locality,
- processing based on dense numeric arrays rather than object-heavy structures,

- reuse of intermediate results within the pipeline to reduce redundant computation, and
- explicit control over algorithm selection through the Strategy pattern.

This pattern combines modularity with data-oriented execution, resulting in both low runtime and low energy consumption. For numeric and data-parallel workloads, this architecture provides the best balance between maintainability and performance.

6.5.2 Moderately Efficient Pattern

The Pipes & Filters architecture performs comparably to the monolithic implementation, with a slight overhead observed in most runs. Its main advantages include:

- clear modular decomposition,
- strong maintainability, and
- straightforward instrumentation and experimentation.

The additional stage boundaries and intermediate buffers introduce a small amount of overhead, mainly due to extra function calls and intermediate array materialisation. However, the overall performance remains close to the monolithic implementation. For research-oriented or extensible systems, Pipes & Filters represents a strong compromise between architectural clarity and runtime efficiency.

6.5.3 Structurally Simple Pattern

The God Monolith implementation demonstrates that a structurally simple design can achieve performance comparable to more modular approaches. Because most of the processing occurs inside a single function, the implementation avoids additional pipeline objects and reduces function call overhead and avoids intermediate data structures.

However, this simplicity also introduces certain drawbacks:

- limited modularity and reuse,
- reduced flexibility when modifying or extending the processing stages, and
- lower maintainability as the codebase grows.

Although the monolithic design performs similarly to the Pipes & Filters implementation in terms of runtime and energy consumption, its tightly coupled structure makes it less suitable for experimentation or long-term system evolution. In practice, such designs are sometimes acceptable for small or performance-focused implementations, but modular architectures generally provide better maintainability for larger systems.

6.5.4 Worst Pattern: Pixel-Decorator Architecture

The Pixel-Decorator design performs dramatically worse than all other variants. The reasons are structural rather than implementation-specific:

- per-pixel object creation,
- dynamic dispatch in hot numeric loops,
- poor cache locality, and
- inability to exploit vectorization or data-parallel execution.

This architecture transforms simple numeric operations into interpreter-heavy object processing. Runtime increases significantly and total energy consumption grows accordingly.

Such designs are unsuitable for computation-heavy workloads.

6.5.5 Practical Guidance for Architecture Selection

Based on the empirical results of this thesis, the following recommendations emerge:

- Prefer data-oriented or pipeline-based designs that operate on contiguous arrays.
- Use modular architectures that preserve locality rather than introducing per-element abstractions.
- Avoid object-oriented indirection inside numeric hot loops.
- Select programming languages with efficient runtime characteristics when execution cost is a primary concern.

6.6 Summary

The experiments demonstrate that sustainability-aware software development is influenced by both architectural design and runtime choice. Architecture primarily determines structural efficiency, while the language runtime strongly influences execution efficiency, and their interaction shapes the overall energy behaviour.

When both are aligned, for example, a data-oriented architecture implemented in a compiled or JIT-optimized language - substantial reductions in runtime and energy consumption can be achieved without altering the underlying mathematical algorithm. These findings reinforce recent energy-aware software engineering research emphasizing that early design and implementation decisions significantly influence downstream energy behaviour during testing and continuous integration phases (Verdecchia et al., 2025).

Chapter 7

Testing Phase

Testing phase is a critical phase within the Software Development Lifecycle (SDLC), ensuring correctness, reliability, and confidence in evolving software systems which was implemented to meet the specified requirements. However, repeated execution of test suites can itself become computationally expensive, particularly when tests involve heavy numerical processing or large parameter spaces. In recent years, software engineering research has increasingly recognised that testing is not only a quality assurance activity but also a contributor to overall energy consumption during development (Verdecchia et al., 2025).

Within this thesis, testing is analysed from an energy-aware perspective. Rather than treating test execution as a fixed process, the objective is to investigate how scheduling, prioritisation, and selective execution influence energy usage while preserving functional confidence. The experiments were conducted on a modular image-processing pipeline developed in Python, where test workloads range from lightweight mathematical unit tests to computationally intensive end-to-end executions.

The testing phase addresses energy-awareness with test-prioritization and selective testing aligning with the principles of the GREEDY_E approach proposed at ICSE 2025 to a fundamentally different domain. While the original work evaluates large Java-based regression suites, this thesis explores whether similar ideas remain effective when test cases correspond to parameterised computational configurations rather than conventional unit methods in Python. For the further experiments, Strategy-based Data-oriented image pipeline is used.

7.1 Testing Architecture

7.1.1 Multi-Level Test Design

The testing infrastructure was intentionally designed as a layered system to reflect realistic development workflows. Three complementary levels were implemented.

Unit tests verify correctness of isolated components such as Gaussian kernel generation, Sobel gradient computation, grayscale conversion, and image input/output utilities. These tests primarily validate mathematical properties, output ranges, and shape consistency.

Integration tests validate interactions between multiple processing stages. Instead of testing functions independently, these tests execute a partial processing pipeline consisting of grayscale

conversion, Gaussian blur, gradient computation, and thresholding. Synthetic image fixtures are used to ensure deterministic behaviour while still representing realistic data flow.

End-to-end (E2E) tests execute the complete command-line pipeline. Each run represents a full processing scenario and therefore incurs substantially higher computational cost. Unlike traditional projects where tests correspond to predefined methods, each configuration of processing parameters (kernel size, sigma, threshold, scaling factor, blur strategy, and iteration count) is treated as an individual test case.

This design transforms testing into a parameter-grid evaluation problem, creating a heterogeneous workload suitable for energy-aware experimentation.

7.1.2 Baseline and Energy-Aware Strategies

Two execution strategies were compared throughout the experiments:

First, the baseline strategy executes all tests in their natural or default order, reflecting conventional regression testing practice. This provides a reference for energy consumption and execution time.

Second, the energy-aware strategy introduces lightweight prioritisation and selection rules. Unit tests marked as computationally expensive were tagged using custom test marker `@pytest.mark.heavy` and excluded from certain runs. Integration tests used a `@critical` marker to represent high-value scenarios. For end-to-end testing, configurations were reordered using a GREEDY_E -inspired heuristic that prioritises low-cost yet diverse configurations first.

Importantly, the objective was not to reduce correctness guarantees but to optimise the order and subset of execution to improve the energy–confidence tradeoff.

7.2 Relation to Existing Research (ICSE 2025)

The GREEDY_E approach proposes energy-aware regression testing by combining diversity-aware prioritisation with energy estimation models (Verdecchia et al., 2025). In the original work, tests are represented as vectors extracted from source-level features and executed within large Java ecosystems.

This thesis differs in several important aspects:

First, the system under study is not a traditional enterprise codebase but a numerical image-processing pipeline. Test cases therefore represent parameter configurations rather than source-level unit methods.

Second, energy measurements are obtained using CodeCarbon rather than hardware instrumentation, providing estimated energy and emissions values during execution.

Third, the prioritisation strategy was implemented manually using lightweight heuristics tailored to the pipeline’s computational characteristics. The cost proxy combines kernel size, scaling factor, iteration count, and blur strategy to approximate relative computational expense.

Despite these methodological differences, behavioural similarities were observed. As reported in the original GREEDY_E study, improvements were negligible for small homogeneous test suites but became visible when workload diversity increased.

This cross-domain consistency suggests that prioritisation effectiveness depends more on workload heterogeneity than on language or framework.

7.3 Experimental Setup

All experiments were executed on an Apple M2 Pro system running macOS 15.7.2 with 32 GB RAM. The test infrastructure was implemented using Python and PyTest, while energy measurements were recorded using CodeCarbon.

A unified tracking wrapper was created to automatically log execution duration, emissions estimates, and test metadata into structured CSV files. This allowed consistent comparison across all test levels.

The end-to-end parameter grid included multiple images and combinations of:

- kernel sizes
- Gaussian sigmas
- threshold values
- blur strategies (separable vs full2d)
- scaling factors
- iteration counts

This produced a heterogeneous test workload suitable for evaluating scheduling effects.

7.4 Results

7.4.1 Unit and Integration Levels

At the unit and integration levels, differences between baseline and energy-aware execution were minimal. Since these suites contain relatively few tests with comparable execution cost, prioritisation has limited influence on total energy consumption. This observation aligns with prior research indicating that energy-aware scheduling becomes meaningful primarily when suites exhibit cost diversity.

7.4.2 End-to-End Grid Evaluation

The strongest effects were observed at the end-to-end level. Although final total energy consumption converges when all tests complete, cumulative energy curves reveal clear differences during execution.

Figure 7.1. Cumulative energy consumption for baseline versus GREEDY_E-inspired ordering.

Table 7.1. Comparison between GREEDY_E and Baseline approaches.

Approach	Total Runs	Total Duration (s)	Total Energy (kWh)	AUC Energy	Energy Saved (%)	Time Saved (%)	AUC Improvement (%)
GREEDY _E	128	844.9306	0.008 21	0.5237	0.3516	0.3465	1.1409
Baseline	128	847.8683	0.008 25	0.5298	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

The End-to-End tests to test the entire pipeline were executed simultaneously once with the baseline approach and then with the GREEDY_E. In the Table 7.1 we can see that the GREEDY_E takes less time and total energy in comparison with the baseline which executes all the tests - yet covering all the important tests that test the entire image pipeline. Time saved is approximately 0.3465% and proportionally energy is also saved around 0.35% with this approach. The area under the cumulative-energy curve (AUC) summarizes how much energy is consumed throughout the test execution, with lower values indicating that less energy is spent earlier in the run. In our case, GREEDY_E achieves a lower AUC than the baseline (0.5237 vs. 0.5298, 1.14% reduction), meaning it provides the same overall test execution with a more energy-efficient execution profile, especially beneficial under time/energy budgets where tests may be stopped before completion.

Therefore, GREEDY_E ordering consistently consumed less energy during early execution phases. This behaviour is particularly relevant in realistic CI scenarios where testing may terminate early due to resource constraints.

7.4.3 Scaled Workloads

Tests were executed sequentially to avoid interference, and static prioritisation assumes stable energy characteristics across runs. It was clearly noticeable that increasing image resolution and parameter diversity amplified differences between strategies. Since computational cost scales non-linearly with image size and kernel complexity, early execution of cheaper configurations produced larger relative savings. This supports the hypothesis that energy-aware testing becomes increasingly beneficial as workloads grow.

7.5 Selective Testing Extension

Beyond prioritisation, this work introduces a lightweight selective testing mechanism based on Git change detection. The system maps source modules to their corresponding test files and executes only the tests impacted by recent changes.

First, explicit source-to-test and test-to-source mappings are defined to identify which tests correspond to which source files. This mapping is implemented using a simple JSON-based configuration that lists dependencies between source modules and test suites.

Second, `git diff` is used to detect changes in the source code. When a source file is modified, the corresponding tests are identified through the mapping and executed, while unaffected tests are skipped. This approach avoids the need for static analysis or complex build systems and remains language-agnostic, making it suitable for research-scale projects.

Figure 7.2. Selective regression testing workflow used in the maintenance experiments.

Unlike industrial build systems such as Bazel or Buck, the implementation remains intentionally transparent and minimal. The selective runner relies only on `git diff` analysis and explicit dependency mapping, requiring minimal infrastructure while remaining applicable across different programming languages. Integrating this selective execution mechanism with energy measurement enables maintenance-related testing costs to be quantified rather than assumed.

7.6 Key Findings

Three major insights emerge from the testing phase:

First, prioritisation strategies provide limited benefit for small homogeneous suites but scale effectively for heterogeneous workloads.

Second, cumulative execution behaviour is more informative than final totals. Energy-aware ordering reduces early consumption, which is relevant for time-bounded testing environments.

Third, lightweight tooling can bridge academic ideas and practical workflows. The implemented selective runner demonstrates that energy-aware testing does not require heavyweight infrastructure to be effective.

7.7 Summary

The testing phase demonstrates that energy-aware testing strategies can reduce cumulative energy usage without sacrificing correctness. By adapting GREEDY_E concepts to a parameterised computational workload and integrating selective regression testing, this work extends energy-aware testing beyond traditional enterprise codebases.

Most importantly, the results reinforce the broader thesis argument: sustainability considerations should influence not only runtime optimisation but also how testing itself is designed, scheduled, and executed throughout the SDLC.

Chapter 8

Deployment Phase

8.1 Deployment-Time Testing and Energy–Confidence Trade-offs

While previous phases focused on architectural design and testing strategies, the deployment phase investigates how *process-level decisions* influence sustainability during Continuous Integration (CI) and deployment workflows. Modern CI pipelines execute large numbers of automated tests repeatedly, often without considering energy implications. Recent research highlights that testing and CI pipelines can contribute significantly to software energy consumption, motivating the need for energy-aware deployment strategies (Lee et al., 2024; Procaccianti et al., 2015; Verdecchia et al., 2025).

The goal of this phase is therefore not to redesign algorithms, but to evaluate how deployment-time test selection affects energy consumption while maintaining sufficient confidence in software correctness.

8.2 Relation to Existing Research

Prior work has shown that CI pipelines are increasingly significant contributors to software energy usage (Procaccianti et al., 2015). GREEDY_E demonstrated that test prioritization can reduce early energy consumption in large suites, particularly when test cost varies significantly (Verdecchia et al., 2025).

The deployment framework developed in this thesis extends these ideas by:

- integrating lightweight selective testing rather than only ordering,
- applying energy measurement directly within CI-like execution, and
- treating test volume as a proxy for deployment confidence.

Unlike industrial-scale systems that rely on complex dependency graphs, the proposed approach remains lightweight, transparent, and adaptable to smaller projects.

8.3 CI/CD Simulation Framework

To emulate realistic deployment conditions, a lightweight CI simulation framework was implemented in Python. The framework executes testing workflows under controlled configurations while measuring runtime and energy consumption using CodeCarbon.

Two deployment strategies were evaluated:

- **Full CI Simulation:** Executes all available unit and integration tests regardless of code changes.
- **Selective CI Simulation:** Executes only tests affected by recent source-code modifications using a Git-diff based selective testing mechanism, previously discussed in Section 7.5.

Both strategies were wrapped using a common energy measurement (`run_suite_with_tracker`), ensuring consistent measurement conditions and comparable metrics.

This setup reflects common industrial CI scenarios, where teams must balance execution cost against confidence in software quality.

8.4 Energy Measurement and Experiment Design During Deployment

8.4.1 Recorded Metrics and Log files

Energy and emissions were recorded using CodeCarbon, which estimates system power consumption and integrates it over time to derive electricity usage and emissions (CodeCarbon contributors, n.d.-a).

For each simulated deployment run, the following metrics were collected:

- Execution duration (seconds)
- Total energy consumption (kWh)
- CPU and RAM energy estimates
- Estimated CO₂e emissions (kg)
- Number of executed tests

All measurements were automatically logged into:

- `test_run_summary.csv`
- `test_case_runs.csv`

This enabled reproducible post-analysis and visualization.

8.4.2 Deployment Experiment Design

The deployment experiments simulate a developer workflow in which code changes trigger CI execution. The experimental procedure was:

1. Modify selected source files or tests.
2. Commit changes to generate realistic Git diffs.
3. Execute Full CI simulation.
4. Execute Selective CI simulation.
5. Record energy, runtime, and test-count metrics.

Selective testing relies on a lightweight mapping between source files and associated tests explained in Section 7.5.

8.5 Results and Visualization

Even though, the test files were not largely scaled, on average the selective CI approach saved approximately 0.40% to 0.50% energy in comparison with the full CI scenario. With a larger codebase, it is expected to save more energy by just targeting the affected files and integrations for testing during deployment instead of running each test suite each time something changes. The collected results were visualized using the following primary plot :

- **Energy Comparison Bar Chart** – average energy consumption (kWh) for full vs. selective CI. The graph is scaled in the y-axis to highlight the relative difference, which is expected to be small but meaningful in aggregate.

Figure 8.1. Energy consumption comparison between Full CI and Selective CI strategies.

The results show a clear reduction in energy consumption when selective testing is applied. Execution time decreased proportionally with the number of executed tests, confirming that deployment-time decisions strongly influence sustainability outcomes.

8.5.1 Interpretation: Energy vs Confidence

Deployment pipelines inherently involve a trade-off between two competing objectives:

- **Energy efficiency** – minimizing computational work.
- **Testing confidence** – maximizing verification coverage.

Running all tests provides maximal confidence but incurs higher energy cost. Selective testing reduces energy usage by executing fewer tests, introducing a controlled reduction in confidence.

This trade-off aligns with findings from GREEDY_E-style energy-aware testing research, which demonstrates that test scheduling and selection strategies can reduce energy consumption without significantly harming practical reliability (Verdecchia et al., 2025).

The experiments suggest:

- For localized code changes, selective testing achieves substantial energy savings with minimal confidence loss.
- For large or high-risk changes, full CI remains preferable despite higher energy consumption.

8.6 Key Findings

The deployment experiments reveal three important insights:

1. Deployment-time test selection is a major energy lever in CI workflows.
2. Selective execution significantly reduces runtime and electricity consumption.
3. Energy-aware deployment decisions should be configurable depending on risk and required confidence level.

These findings support the broader thesis claim that sustainability considerations should extend beyond implementation and testing into deployment workflows.

8.7 Summary

The deployment phase demonstrates that CI configuration and test-selection policies directly influence software energy consumption. While full test execution maximizes confidence, selective deployment strategies can achieve substantial energy savings when changes are localized.

This phase confirms that energy-aware software engineering must extend beyond code-level optimization toward deployment-time decision making. By integrating lightweight selective

testing with energy tracking, the proposed framework offers a practical path toward greener CI pipelines.

Future work may incorporate dynamic dependency analysis, energy-budget constraints, executing this approach with CI parallelization, and adaptive CI scheduling to further optimize the energy–confidence trade-off.

Chapter 9

Maintenance Phase

The energy-aware maintenance phase investigates how architectural refactoring patterns influence energy consumption during software maintenance and system evolution. While previous phases of this thesis focused on energy-aware testing strategies (Chapter 7) and deployment-time CI configuration tradeoffs (Chapter 8), the maintenance phase shifts attention toward long-term sustainability.

Maintenance activities dominate the lifecycle of most software systems. During this phase, developers continuously modify source code, execute regression tests, and re-establish confidence before deployment. Although refactoring is traditionally evaluated in terms of maintainability or runtime performance, its impact on the energy cost of maintaining testing confidence remains insufficiently explored.

The central hypothesis investigated in this phase is:

Architectural modularization enables more proportional regression testing, thereby reducing the energy required to maintain confidence during maintenance activities.

Rather than treating refactoring solely as a runtime optimization technique, this work evaluates refactoring as a structural mechanism that affects regression testing effort and CI-level energy consumption.

Existing research on energy-aware refactoring primarily focuses on runtime improvements, including performance optimization, energy reduction in mobile applications, and micro-level code optimizations (Lago et al., 2015; Pinto et al., 2015).

However, relatively little attention has been given to:

- The energy cost of regression testing after code evolution,
- Energy consumption during maintenance workflows,
- The relationship between architectural modularity and CI-level energy usage.

This chapter addresses this gap by introducing a maintenance-oriented perspective: refactoring is analyzed as an architectural enabler that reduces the energy footprint required to preserve testing confidence during evolution.

9.1 Experimental Design

9.1.1 Pre-Refactored Architecture

Originally, the image-processing pipeline followed a more non-modular single-file style:

- Core functionality was not clearly modularized.
- Mapping between source modules and tests was coarse.
- Small changes frequently triggered broad regression execution.

As a result, maintenance activities often required running the full unit and integration test suites regardless of the localized scope of modification.

9.1.2 Refactored Architecture

To improve maintainability and enable proportional testing, the pipeline was refactored into modular components:

```
core/  
  gaussian.py  
  grayscale.py  
  sobel.py  
  magnitude.py  
  io_utils.py
```

Each module encapsulates a single processing stage. In addition, the following structural changes were introduced:

- Separation of unit and integration tests.
- Definition of a dependency-based impact map.
- Implementation of a Git-driven selective test runner.
- Generation of commit-level JSON artifacts documenting change impact.

These changes enabled fine-grained traceability between source modifications and corresponding tests.

9.2 Maintenance-Aware Selective Testing Implementation

9.2.1 Change Detection

Maintenance simulations were performed using real Git commits as discussed in Chapter 7. For each maintenance event:

- `git diff` was used to detect modified files.
- Modified modules were mapped to impacted tests.
- Only relevant unit and integration tests were executed.

This process mirrors realistic CI workflows while remaining reproducible.

9.2.2 Impact Artifact Generation

Each maintenance event produced a JSON artifact containing:

- Commit hash
- Changed files
- Impacted modules
- Executed tests
- Execution results

These artifacts provide transparent evidence of proportional regression execution and allow maintenance decisions to be audited.

9.2.3 Maintenance Event Artifacts for Selective Regression

To ensure that maintenance-phase regression decisions are transparent and reproducible, each simulated maintenance change produces a structured JSON artifact. This artifact records the changed files detected via Git, the impacted tests chosen by the selective runner, and the exact `pytest` command executed. Example JSON artifact generated after changing Sobel-related code (and some files around it) is shown in Listing 9.2.3.

```

1 {
2   "timestamp_utc": "2026-02-15T22:31:26.146596",
3   "base": "HEAD~1",
4   "repo_root": "/Users/abhishek.patel/Desktop/Bach_Thes",
5   "changed_files": [
6     "Image pipeline Python/Data_Oriented/energy_logs/emissions.csv",
7     "Image pipeline Python/Data_Oriented/energy_logs/powermetrics_log.
8       txt",
9     "Image pipeline Python/Data_Oriented/refactored/core/sobel.py",
10    "Image pipeline Python/Data_Oriented/refactored/
11      maintenance_rq6_experiments.py",
12    "Image pipeline Python/Data_Oriented/refactored/
13      selective_test_runner.py",
14    "Image pipeline Python/Data_Oriented/test_run_summary.csv"
15  ],
16  "impacted_tests": [
17    "refactored/tests/integration/test_pipeline_stages.py",
18    "refactored/tests/unit/test_sobel_and_mag.py"
19  ]
20 }

```

```

16 ],
17 "pytest_cmd": [
18     "pytest",
19     "-q",
20     "refactored/tests/integration/test_pipeline_stages.py",
21     "refactored/tests/unit/test_sobel_and_mag.py"
22 ]
23 }

```

Listing 9.2.3 shows one maintenance event where the Sobel stage implementation (`core/sobel.py`) was modified. The selective runner identified only two impacted tests: a focused unit test validating the Sobel and magnitude logic, and an integration test validating end-to-end stage interaction. This demonstrates the central maintenance hypothesis of this thesis: modular refactoring enables proportional regression testing, which reduces unnecessary computation and thus lowers the energy required to re-establish confidence after code changes.

9.3 Measurements and Evaluation

This section quantifies the effects of maintenance-aware selective regression testing using three measurement categories: (i) runtime and energy impact, (ii) confidence scope, and (iii) CI-like execution behavior. Throughout this evaluation, the maintenance event shown in Listing 9.2.3 is used as the concrete reference example: a localized change in the Sobel stage (`refactored/core/sobel.py`) triggers only the Sobel unit test and the pipeline-stage integration test, instead of the full regression suite.

9.3.1 Runtime and Energy Impact

To measure the operational cost of regression testing during maintenance, each run was wrapped with CodeCarbon’s `EmissionsTracker`. Energy impact is operationalized via two complementary outputs: wall-clock duration (seconds) and estimated CO₂e emissions (kg) as a stable energy proxy, although additional metrics could be analyzed, this evaluation focuses on duration and CO₂e as stable, reproducible comparative indicators. This is appropriate for comparative analysis because the CO₂e estimate is derived from the same measurement process and hardware context across approaches, allowing relative differences between *full* and *selective* regression execution to be interpreted consistently.

Figure 9.1 compares the average execution time per maintenance regression run for the two strategies for the Sobel maintenance event (Listing 9.2.3), where only two tests were executed, which is representative of the broader pattern observed across localized changes: refactoring and explicit source-to-test mapping enable regression time to scale with change size rather than with overall project size. The selective approach reduces runtime by approximately 45% for this scenario by avoiding redundant test execution unrelated to the changed module(s).

Figure 9.1. Maintenance regression runtime comparison (full vs. selective).

Figure 9.2 reports the corresponding CO₂e emissions (energy proxy) for the same runs. While absolute emissions values are small in this experimental setup, the qualitative trend is consistent: selective regression reduces the maintenance-phase energy footprint by eliminating unnecessary computation. Importantly, this reduction is not achieved by weakening the test logic itself, but by preventing unrelated tests from being re-executed when the change scope is localized. For the sobel maintenance event, full regression execution exhibited approximately two orders of magnitude higher CO₂e emissions compared to selective execution.

Figure 9.2. Maintenance regression energy proxy comparison (full vs. selective).

Together, Figures 9.1 and 9.2 support the maintenance hypothesis of this chapter: architectural modularization enables proportional regression, which reduces both runtime and energy cost of re-establishing correctness after code evolution.

9.3.2 Confidence Scope

The second measurement category concerns *confidence*, i.e., how much verification is performed after a maintenance change. In a practical SDLC setting, confidence is typically established through the combination of test execution and test adequacy metrics (e.g., coverage). For this thesis, the primary confidence proxy is the *number of executed tests* under each strategy, because selective regression changes the executed subset by design.

In the Sobel maintenance event (Listing 9.2.3), the selective runner executed exactly the tests mapped to the modified module: one focused unit test validating Sobel/magnitude behavior and one integration test validating the pipeline-stage interaction. This demonstrates that selective regression does not eliminate testing; rather, it concentrates verification effort on the affected feature boundary. The full-suite approach, in contrast, provides broader confidence by construction but incurs additional cost that is not proportional to the change size.

This framing directly supports the thesis-wide energy-per-confidence perspective: maintenance workflows should aim to preserve sufficient confidence while minimizing unnecessary computation. Selective regression improves this tradeoff by reducing the denominator (energy/time) more aggressively than it reduces the numerator (verification confidence), particularly when changes are localized.

9.3.3 CI-Level Simulation under Maintenance Conditions

Finally, maintenance-phase regressions were treated as *CI-like events*. In modern development workflows, even small commits often trigger automated verification pipelines. Therefore, the selective runner was evaluated under the same execution assumptions as the CI simulation described in Chapter 8: non-interactive execution, standardized commands, and reproducible configuration.

The JSON artifact mechanism is essential for this CI framing. Each maintenance event yields an auditable record of (i) which files changed, (ii) which tests were selected, and (iii) the exact command executed. This provides two practical benefits relevant to CI/CD: (1) traceability, because stakeholders can inspect which verification steps were run for a given change; and (2) reproducibility, because the same command can be replayed to validate or debug the outcome.

In summary, the maintenance evaluation demonstrates that refactoring not only influences the runtime performance of the application but also affects the operational cost of software evolution. By enabling selective regression, modular refactoring reduces the energy required to maintain confidence across changes, making the maintenance phase itself more sustainable.

9.4 Key Findings

9.4.1 Refactoring Enables Proportional Maintenance

The modular architecture allowed localized changes to trigger only relevant tests. Consequently:

- Regression scope decreased,
- CI execution became proportional to change size,

- Energy consumption during maintenance decreased.

9.4.2 Energy Savings Are Structural

Unlike Chapter 7 and Chapter 8, where improvements were achieved through execution strategy, this chapter demonstrates that:

- Energy savings can emerge from architectural structure itself.
- Modularity determines how efficiently regression scales during evolution.

9.4.3 Maintenance-Energy Evaluation Is Underexplored

Most refactoring studies evaluate readability or runtime metrics. This work extends prior research by incorporating:

- CI-level energy analysis,
- Change-impact proportionality,
- Sustainability of regression testing.

9.4.4 Contribution Relative to Existing Work

The following changes represent the main contributions introduced in this phase:

- Refactoring from non-modular and single file style into stage-based modules.
- Introduction of a lightweight Git-based impact analysis workflow.
- Integration of energy measurements into maintenance evaluation.
- Use of JSON artifacts for traceable regression decisions.
- Framing refactoring as an SDLC sustainability mechanism rather than only a runtime optimization.

While regression test selection techniques already exist (Elsner et al., 2022; Gligorić, 2015), this work connects architectural refactoring with measurable maintenance-phase energy behavior.

9.5 Summary

This chapter demonstrates that refactoring patterns influence not only the runtime performance but also the maintenance-phase energy consumption. Modular architectures enable proportional regression testing, reducing energy expenditure required to maintain testing confidence.

These results reinforce the thesis-wide conclusion that energy-aware SDLC practices must extend beyond runtime optimization and include architectural and maintenance decisions.

Chapter 10

Conclusion and Future Directions

10.1 Overview

This thesis investigated energy-aware decision making across the entire Software Development Lifecycle (SDLC). Rather than restricting sustainability considerations to runtime optimization alone, this work treated energy consumption as a cross-phase engineering concern, beginning at requirements and extending through design, development, testing, deployment, and maintenance.

The central premise of this research is that energy efficiency is not an isolated optimization but a structural property of software systems. It emerges from early requirement framing, architectural design decisions, language-runtime characteristics, testing strategy, CI configuration, and long-term maintainability practices.

By evaluating these lifecycle phases systematically, this thesis demonstrates that sustainable software engineering must be lifecycle-aware rather than phase-isolated.

10.2 Key Findings Across the Lifecycle

10.2.1 Energy Awareness Begins at Requirements

Energy efficiency must be treated as both:

- a technical requirement or constraint (e.g., bounded energy consumption or performance limits), and
- a sustainability-oriented requirement (e.g., sustainability goals or environmental impact constraints).

When energy awareness is introduced during requirements engineering, it influences architectural choices, tooling decisions, and verification strategies. This aligns with sustainable software engineering perspectives that advocate embedding sustainability into system requirements rather than retrofitting optimizations later (Lago et al., 2015).

10.2.2 Architectural Design Determines Structural Energy Behavior

The comparative architectural evaluation demonstrated that when the underlying mathematical workload remains constant, architectural structure still influences runtime and energy characteristics.

Efficient designs:

- Preserve contiguous data flow
- Minimize abstraction overhead in performance-critical paths
- Enable modular substitution through structured patterns (e.g., Strategy-based Data-Oriented Design)
- Support proportional system evolution

In contrast, abstraction-heavy and object-per-element designs increase instruction counts, memory indirection, and cache pressure, leading to disproportionate energy waste. In contrast, abstraction-heavy and object-per-element designs increase instruction counts, memory indirection, and cache pressure, leading to disproportionate energy waste. Consequently, architectural selection remains a critical factor in determining energy behavior, even when the underlying algorithmic logic is identical.

10.2.3 Programming Language and Runtime Matter

Cross-language experiments confirmed that identical architectural and algorithmic logic produce different runtime and energy profiles depending on execution environment.

- JIT-compiled environments optimize hot loops and reduce interpreter overhead.
- Interpreted runtimes incur dynamic dispatch and object-management costs.
- Low-level languages may offer superior performance but are typically considered better suited for performance-critical subsystems.

These findings align with empirical studies comparing programming language energy efficiency (Pereira et al., 2021), indicating that language selection must align with system goals by balancing runtime efficiency with contextual considerations such as maintainability.

10.2.4 Energy-Aware Testing Reduces Waste and Improves Feedback

The evaluation of GREEDY_E-inspired prioritization demonstrated that:

- Benefits increase with test-suite size and heterogeneity
- Early cumulative energy consumption decreases under prioritized execution
- Verification confidence can be maintained while reshaping energy profiles

Energy-aware test prioritization reduces unnecessary early energy consumption and improves feedback efficiency without compromising correctness.

10.2.5 Deployment-Time Configuration Enables Energy–Confidence Tradeoffs

CI simulation experiments revealed that selective test execution based on change impact:

- Reduces execution time
- Reduces CO₂e emissions
- Maintains targeted verification confidence

Rather than treating CI pipelines as static full-suite executors, this thesis frames deployment-time verification as a configurable energy-confidence tradeoff. Hence, CI systems should support adaptive regression strategies rather than unconditional full-suite execution.

10.2.6 Maintenance-Phase Refactoring Reduces Lifecycle Energy

The maintenance-phase evaluation demonstrated that modular refactoring enables proportional regression testing. By decomposing a monolithic pipeline into stage-based modules and introducing Git-driven selective regression, regression effort scaled with change size rather than project size.

Unlike prior refactoring research that focuses primarily on runtime performance or readability (Pinto et al., 2015), this thesis evaluates refactoring through an energy-per-confidence lens.

10.3 Integrated Lifecycle Perspective

Across all phases, a consistent pattern emerges:

1. Requirements determine whether energy is treated as a constraint.
2. Architecture determines structural efficiency and evolvability.
3. Programming language influences computational cost.
4. Testing strategy reshapes verification energy profiles.
5. Deployment configuration determines CI energy behavior.
6. Maintenance structure determines long-term regression cost.

Taken together, these observations emphasize that energy efficiency in SDLC is not the outcome of isolated optimizations but of coordinated engineering decisions throughout the software lifecycle. Treating sustainability as an explicit concern during requirements, architecture, development, testing, deployment, and maintenance enables systems to remain both structurally efficient and evolutionarily sustainable. Energy-aware software engineering therefore emerges not as a single technique, but as an integrated lifecycle discipline.

10.4 Future Directions

While this thesis demonstrates that energy-aware decisions across the SDLC influence both runtime efficiency and lifecycle sustainability, several opportunities exist to extend and deepen this research.

10.4.1 Higher-Precision Energy Measurement

Energy measurements in this thesis were obtained using model-based estimation (CodeCarbon), which provides consistent and reproducible comparative metrics. However, future work could incorporate hardware-level energy counters such as RAPL (Running Average Power Limit) or external power measurement devices.

Such instrumentation would:

- Increase measurement granularity
- Enable component-level isolation (CPU, memory, I/O)
- Strengthen statistical validity across repeated trials

More precise instrumentation would allow deeper investigation of micro-architectural effects and enable more rigorous benchmarking across environments.

10.4.2 Expanded Architectural Exploration

This thesis evaluated four architectural styles within a computer-vision pipeline context. While these represent distinct design philosophies (monolithic, pipeline-based, strategy-oriented, and abstraction-heavy), the architectural search space is significantly larger.

Future research may explore the following architectural paradigms with energy-aware evaluation:

- Event-driven architectures
- Reactive and streaming systems
- Parallel and distributed pipeline designs
- GPU-accelerated or heterogeneous compute architectures

Furthermore, extending evaluation beyond computer vision into domains such as data engineering, scientific computing, web backends, or embedded systems would strengthen generalizability.

10.4.3 Programming Language and Runtime Consistency

Although this thesis compared selected languages under identical algorithmic logic, further work could expand toward:

- Consistent multi-language benchmarking frameworks

- Just-In-Time vs Ahead-Of-Time compilation effects
- Memory management strategies (Garbage Collection vs manual)
- Hybrid systems combining high-level orchestration with low-level kernels

Application-based language selection strategies could also be formalized, distinguishing between:

- Orchestration layers
- Performance-critical subsystems
- Rapid prototyping environments

This would bridge practical engineering constraints with measurable energy impact.

10.4.4 Automated and Adaptive Testing Strategies

The testing phase demonstrated benefits of prioritization and selective regression. However, several extensions are possible:

- Fully automated change-impact graph generation
- Dynamic test selection using dependency tracing
- Integration of coverage metrics into energy-confidence optimization
- Machine-learning-assisted prioritization strategies

Additionally, scaling experiments to large industrial test suites would allow validation of the energy-per-confidence model under realistic CI/CD workloads.

10.4.5 Deployment-Level Expansion

The deployment phase in this thesis focused primarily on CI-based regression testing. In real-world systems, deployment also includes:

- Artifact packaging and containerization
- Infrastructure provisioning
- Cloud resource allocation
- Rolling updates and rollback mechanisms

Future work may investigate energy-aware deployment strategies across cloud platforms such as AWS, Google Cloud, and Azure, incorporating:

- Auto-scaling policies

- Instance type selection
- Regional energy intensity differences
- Minor vs major release strategies

Particularly relevant is the distinction between small patch deployments and large feature releases, as minor fixes may not justify full regression or infrastructure reallocation. Energy-aware deployment heuristics could significantly reduce operational waste in high-frequency release environments.

10.4.6 Maintenance at Industrial Scale

The maintenance-phase experiments demonstrated proportional regression benefits within a moderate-scale system. Future research should evaluate:

- Large enterprise repositories
- Monorepo architectures
- Multi-team CI pipelines
- Dependency-heavy ecosystems

Automated impact analysis and regression selection could be integrated with modern build systems and version-control platforms to evaluate scalability and robustness under complex dependency graphs.

10.4.7 Lifecycle-Level Integration Models

Finally, a promising direction lies in integrating all SDLC phases into a unified optimization framework. Rather than analyzing requirements, architecture, testing, deployment, and maintenance independently, future systems could:

- Model energy impact predictions at design time
- Simulate lifecycle energy budgets
- Provide decision-support tools for architects and DevOps engineers
- Embed sustainability metrics into software governance dashboards

Such integrated frameworks would move beyond retrospective measurement and toward predictive energy-aware engineering.

Closing Perspective

This thesis demonstrates that energy efficiency is influenced by decisions at every stage of the SDLC. Future research should therefore move toward scalable, automated, and cross-domain validation of lifecycle-aware sustainability strategies.

The next step is not merely improving isolated optimizations, but building systematic, tool-supported methodologies that allow organizations to engineer sustainability deliberately and consistently.

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Appendix A

Experimental Environment

A.1 Experimental Environment

All experiments were executed on a workstation with the following configuration:

- Processor: Apple M2 Pro (10 CPU cores)
- Memory: 32 GB RAM
- Operating System: macOS 15.7.2
- Python version: 3.11 (later used 3.12 for some experiments and then 3.13 for the last runs using venv)
- Java version: OpenJDK 21
- Rust version: 1.75

Energy measurements were obtained using the CodeCarbon framework (version 3.1.0, later updated). Power measurements were sampled every second using the parameter `measure_power_secs=1`. The framework internally utilizes the `powermetrics` utility on macOS to collect power data, which provides insights into CPU and GPU energy consumption. For more details on the `powermetrics` utility, refer to its documentation (Mozilla, n.d.).

Appendix B

Parameter Grid

B.1 Experimental Parameter Grid

The experimental evaluation of the image-processing pipeline was conducted using a systematic parameter grid that combines variations in input images and algorithmic configuration parameters. The grid explores how different processing configurations influence runtime performance and energy consumption.

The evaluated parameters correspond to key stages of the pipeline, including Gaussian blurring, edge detection, and scaling operations.

Parameter	Values
Images	High quality images in total: 11
Kernel size	7
Sigma	1.0, 1.4, 2.0
Threshold	0.2, 0.3, 0.4
Iterations	3
Scale factors	1.0, 1.5

Table B.1. Experimental parameter grid used for evaluation

Each parameter influences a specific stage of the image-processing pipeline:

- **Kernel size:** Defines the size of the Gaussian blur kernel used for smoothing the input image.
- **Sigma:** Represents the standard deviation of the Gaussian kernel, controlling the intensity of the blur.
- **Threshold:** Determines the threshold used during edge magnitude filtering.
- **Blur strategy:** Specifies the implementation of the Gaussian blur operation, either using a separable convolution or a full two-dimensional convolution.
- **Iterations:** Number of repeated executions of the pipeline for the same configuration.
- **Scale factors:** Determines the resizing factor applied to the input image before processing.

The parameter grid results in a total of 36 unique configurations:

$$1 \times 3 \times 3 \times 1 \times 2 = 18$$

where each dimension corresponds to one parameter in Table B.

Each configuration was executed multiple times to reduce measurement noise and improve the reliability of the collected energy and runtime metrics.

The configurations were passed to the experimental pipeline via command-line arguments. One example of the input would be:

```
<architecture file with directory>\
--input images/ \
--ksize=7 \
--sigma=2.0 \
--threshold=0.6 \
--iterations=3 \
--scale=2.0
```


Figure B.1. Experimental workflow from parameter generation to energy measurement and result logging.

During execution, the pipeline processed all the input images from the image directory according to the specified parameters and recorded runtime and energy measurements using the instrumentation. The resulting measurements were aggregated and analyzed to evaluate the relationship between algorithmic configuration, performance behavior, and energy consumption. A sample image of the processing stages is shown in Figure B.1.

Appendix C

Detailed Experiment

C.1 Image Pipeline Inputs and Results

The image-processing pipeline produces several intermediate and final outputs for each configuration and the input image. One of the intermediate input images to the strategy oriented pipeline is shown in the Figure C.1. The dimensions of this image are 3000 x 4238 pixels. Multiple such images (generally 11) were used as input to the pipeline to evaluate the performance and energy consumption across different configurations.

Figure C.1. Sample input image for the strategy-oriented image-processing pipeline.

Intermediate Configuration: Scale factor: 1.5, Blur strategy: separable, Kernel size: 7, Sigma: 1.4, Threshold: 0.3, Iterations: 3

Generated Outputs: The pipeline generates several intermediate outputs such as the blurred image, grayscale image, edge magnitude image(sobel x and sobel y), magnitude image, and the threshold image. A sample of these outputs for the above configuration is shown in the Figures C.2 to C.7. Each output corresponds to a specific stage in the image-processing pipeline, providing insights into how the input image is transformed at each step of the processing.

Figure C.2. Grayscale image.

Figure C.3. Blurred image after Gaussian filtering.

Figure C.4. Sobel X gradient image.

Figure C.5. Sobel Y gradient image.

Figure C.6. Gradient magnitude image.

Figure C.7. Thresholded edge image.

Description of Outputs: The outputs are as follows:

- **Gray**: The grayscale version of the original input image, used as the single-channel basis for subsequent processing stages.
- **Blur**: The Gaussian-smoothed image produced after applying the selected blur strategy, reducing noise and small-scale intensity variations.
- **Sobel_x**: The horizontal gradient response of the image, highlighting intensity changes along the x-direction.
- **Sobel_y**: The vertical gradient response of the image, highlighting intensity changes along the y-direction.
- **Magnitude**: The normalized gradient magnitude image computed from the Sobel_x and Sobel_y responses, representing overall edge strength.
- **Threshold**: The binary edge map obtained by applying a threshold to the magnitude image, retaining only edges above the selected cutoff.

C.2 Example CodeCarbon Measurement Output

To ensure transparency of the energy measurement process, this section provides an example of the raw measurement data produced by the CodeCarbon framework during the execution of the strategy-based pipeline architecture.

CodeCarbon records multiple system-level metrics during each run, including execution duration, estimated power consumption of system components, total energy usage, and estimated CO₂e emissions.

Table C.1 presents a simplified example of the measurement output for several runs of the Strategy + Data-Oriented pipeline configuration. The full CSV output generated during the experiments contains additional metadata fields such as geographic location, operating system information, and hardware configuration, all the fields are shown below:

```
timestamp,project_name,run_id,experiment_id,duration,emissions,emissions_rate,
cpu_power,gpu_power,ram_power,cpu_energy,gpu_energy,ram_energy,
energy_consumed,water_consumed,country_name,country_iso_code,region,
cloud_provider,cloud_region,os,python_version,codecarbon_version,cpu_count,
cpu_model,gpu_count,gpu_model,longitude,latitude,ram_total_size,tracking_mode,
on_cloud,pue,wue
```

Table C.1. Example measurement output generated by CodeCarbon for the Strategy-based pipeline architecture

Time (s)	CO ₂ e (kg)	Electricity (kWh)	CPU Power (W)	GPU Power (W)	CPU Energy (kWh)	RAM Energy (kWh)
298.10	0.000392	0.000929	6.55	0.0060	0.000528	0.000393
300.45	0.000396	0.000942	6.73	0.0061	0.000540	0.000395
301.90	0.000398	0.000950	6.89	0.0062	0.000552	0.000397
303.20	0.000402	0.000962	7.02	0.0061	0.000556	0.000399
301.60	0.000397	0.000945	6.91	0.0060	0.000548	0.000396
301.05	0.000397	0.000941	6.82	0.0061	0.000545	0.000396

Appendix D

Java and Rust Results

D.1 Java Results

The following tables present the results of the energy consumption and performance measurements for the different architectural patterns implemented in Java. Each table corresponds to a specific architectural pattern, showing the time taken, CO₂e emissions, electricity consumed, CPU power, CPU energy, and RAM energy for five runs, along with their mean values.

Table D.1. Strategy + SoA pipeline implemented in Java (5 runs + mean).

Time (s)	CO ₂ e (kg)	Electricity (kWh)	CPU Power (W)	CPU Energy (kWh)	RAM Energy (kWh)
134.08	0.0001434	0.0003586	3.5932	0.0001343	0.0002243
132.04	0.0001413	0.0003533	3.5941	0.0001324	0.0002210
134.51	0.0001434	0.0003585	3.5878	0.0001342	0.0002244
134.78	0.0001444	0.0003610	3.5860	0.0001350	0.0002259
134.15	0.0001435	0.0003588	3.5956	0.0001344	0.0002244
133.91	0.0001432	0.0003580	3.5913	0.0001341	0.0002240

Table D.2. Pipes and Filters pipeline implemented in Java (5 runs + mean).

Time (s)	CO ₂ e (kg)	Electricity (kWh)	CPU Power (W)	CPU Energy (kWh)	RAM Energy (kWh)
173.64	0.0001853	0.0004633	3.5990	0.0001737	0.0002896
168.65	0.0001800	0.0004500	3.5990	0.0001687	0.0002813
167.26	0.0001788	0.0004470	3.5958	0.0001675	0.0002795
170.24	0.0001821	0.0004551	3.5958	0.0001706	0.0002846
172.16	0.0001842	0.0004605	3.5957	0.0001726	0.0002879
170.39	0.0001821	0.0004552	3.5971	0.0001706	0.0002846

Table D.3. God Monolith pipeline implemented in Java (5 runs + mean).

Time (s)	CO ₂ e (kg)	Electricity (kWh)	CPU Power (W)	CPU Energy (kWh)	RAM Energy (kWh)
151.07	0.0001615	0.0004038	3.5873	0.0001511	0.0002527
149.07	0.0001595	0.0003988	3.5941	0.0001494	0.0002494
149.11	0.0001595	0.0003987	3.5922	0.0001493	0.0002494
148.99	0.0001595	0.0003988	3.5915	0.0001493	0.0002495
148.31	0.0001585	0.0003962	3.5957	0.0001485	0.0002477
149.31	0.0001597	0.0003993	3.5922	0.0001495	0.0002497

Table D.4. Pixel Decorator pipeline implemented in Java (5 runs + mean).

Time (s)	CO ₂ e (kg)	Electricity (kWh)	CPU Power (W)	CPU Energy (kWh)	RAM Energy (kWh)
371.94	0.0003996	0.0011990	7.2550	0.0007499	0.0006226
362.98	0.0003890	0.0011725	7.2535	0.0007314	0.0006061
363.47	0.0003895	0.0011737	7.2791	0.0007348	0.0006061
369.66	0.0003971	0.0011926	7.2365	0.0007428	0.0006192
372.16	0.0003995	0.0011986	7.2426	0.0007490	0.0006228
368.04	0.0003949	0.0011873	7.2533	0.0007416	0.0006154

D.2 Rust Results

The following tables present the results for the two architectures Pipes&Filters and Pixel-Decorator implementations in Rust. The results show that the Rust implementation achieves significantly shorter execution times compared to the Java and Python implementations, while also consuming less energy and producing lower CO₂e emissions. This further supports the observation that compiled languages can offer substantial performance benefits for compute-intensive workloads, while also highlighting the importance of architectural design in achieving energy efficiency across different runtime environments.

Table D.5. Pipes and Filters pipeline implemented in Rust (5 runs + mean).

Time (s)	CO ₂ e (kg)	Electricity (kWh)	CPU Power (W)	CPU Energy (kWh)	RAM Energy (kWh)
35.17	0.0000509	0.0001273	6.8965	0.0000670	0.0000583
35.15	0.0000518	0.0001296	7.1326	0.0000693	0.0000583
34.15	0.0000435	0.0001087	5.3067	0.0000501	0.0000567
36.14	0.0000560	0.0001399	7.7917	0.0000779	0.0000600
34.15	0.0000430	0.0001074	5.1753	0.0000489	0.0000567
34.95	0.0000494	0.0001226	6.4606	0.0000627	0.0000580

Table D.6. Pixel-Decorator pipeline implemented in Rust (5 runs + mean).

Time (s)	CO ₂ e (kg)	Electricity (kWh)	CPU Power (W)	CPU Energy (kWh)	RAM Energy (kWh)
79.35	0.0000995	0.0002487	5.1340	0.0001127	0.0001317
78.30	0.0000929	0.0002323	4.5229	0.0000980	0.0001300
79.32	0.0000953	0.0002383	4.6608	0.0001023	0.0001317
79.33	0.0000933	0.0002332	4.4252	0.0000971	0.0001317
78.33	0.0000942	0.0002354	4.6642	0.0001011	0.0001300
78.93	0.0000950	0.0002376	4.6814	0.0001022	0.0001310

Overall, the tables are internally consistent: CO₂e emissions scale proportionally with electricity consumption, and total electricity closely follows the sum of CPU and RAM energy. Runtime also correlates strongly with RAM energy, reflecting the near-constant RAM power model. Minor deviations might be observed between the reported mean CPU power and integrated CPU energy, but the overall trends remain coherent and comparable across architectures.

Appendix E

Implementation Snippets

This appendix presents selected implementation excerpts from the experimental framework used throughout the thesis. Rather than reproducing the complete codebase, it focuses on the core mechanisms that support the study, including pipeline execution, energy tracking, GREEDY_E-inspired ordering, and selective regression testing. The following snippets illustrate how the system was instrumented to enable energy-aware experimentation across multiple SDLC phases.

E.1 Pipeline Execution Loop

Listing E.1 shows the core execution loop of the image-processing pipeline. For each input image, the framework iterates over scaling factors, Gaussian blur parameters, thresholds, and iteration counts. Each configuration is treated as an individual experimental test case.

Listing E.1. Core parameterized pipeline execution loop.

```
1 for path in imgs:
2     base = os.path.splitext(os.path.basename(path))[0]
3     rgb0 = load_rgb_f32(path)
4
5     for sc in scales:
6         rgb = resize_scale(rgb0, sc)
7         gray = gray_op.apply(rgb)
8
9         for s in sigmas:
10            blur = GaussianFilter(strategy, sigma=s, ksize=args.ksize)
11
12            for thr in thrs:
13                g = gray
14                for _ in range(args.iterations):
15                    blurred = blur.apply(g)
16                    gx, gy = sob_op.apply(blurred)
17                    mag, thr_img = MagnitudeAndThreshold(thr).apply(gx, gy)
18                    g = mag
19
20            combo = (
21                f"{base}_scale{sc:g}_sigma{s:g}_"
22                f"k{args.ksize}_thr{thr:g}_it{args.iterations}"
```

```

23     )
24     od = os.path.join(args.outdir, combo)
25     ensure_dir(od)
26
27     save_gray(os.path.join(od, "01_gray.png"), gray)
28     save_gray(os.path.join(od, "02_blur.png"), blurred)
29     save_gray(os.path.join(od, "03_sobel_x.png"), gx)
30     save_gray(os.path.join(od, "04_sobel_y.png"), gy)
31     save_gray(os.path.join(od, "05_magnitude.png"), mag)
32     save_gray(os.path.join(od, "06_threshold.png"), thr_img)

```

The loop structure highlights the computational nature of the system under test. Rather than executing a fixed set of unit methods, the experimental framework evaluates a large parameter grid in which each configuration represents a distinct workload.

E.2 CodeCarbon Tracker Setup

Energy measurements in the Python implementation were collected using CodeCarbon. Listing E.2 shows the tracker initialization used to wrap entire experimental runs.

Listing E.2. CodeCarbon tracker setup for suite-level energy measurement.

```

1 tracker = EmissionsTracker(
2     project_name=f"{test_type}_{approach}",
3     output_dir="energy_logs",
4     log_level="error",
5     measure_power_secs=1,
6     save_to_file=True,
7 )
8
9 tracker.start()
10 t0 = time.time()
11
12 try:
13     suite_result = suite_fn()
14 finally:
15     emissions_kg = tracker.stop()
16     duration_sec = time.time() - t0

```

This setup was reused across testing, deployment, and maintenance experiments to ensure consistency of timing and emissions estimates. The resulting measurements were stored in structured CSV files for later aggregation and visualization.

E.3 GREEDY_E-Inspired Ordering Logic

To adapt the ICSE 2025 GREEDY_E idea to the image-processing workload, each end-to-end test configuration was represented as a numerical feature vector and assigned a rough energy cost estimate. The prioritization logic then combined diversity and energy-awareness when choosing the next configuration to execute.

Listing E.3 shows the core ordering strategy.

Listing E.3. GREEDY_E-inspired configuration ordering.

```
1 def estimate_energy_score(cfg: GridConfig) -> float:
2     strategy_factor = 2.0 if cfg.blur_strategy == "full2d" else 1.0
3     return (
4         (cfg.scale ** 2)
5         * (cfg.ksize ** 2)
6         * num_sigmas
7         * num_thresholds
8         * cfg.iterations
9         * strategy_factor
10    )
11 def greedy_energy_aware_order(configs: List[GridConfig],
12                               k_candidates: int = 30) -> List[GridConfig]:
13     """
14     GREEDYE-inspired:
15     - maintain a prioritized set,
16     - at each step find the k most dissimilar remaining configs,
17     - among them, pick the one with lowest estimated energy.
18     """
19     if not configs:
20         return []
21
22     vecs = {cfg.id: config_vector(cfg) for cfg in configs}
23     remaining = {cfg.id: cfg for cfg in configs}
24     prioritized: List[GridConfig] = []
25
26     # start with the cheapest config (energy-wise)
27     first_id = min(remaining.keys(), key=lambda cid: estimate_energy_score(remaining[
28     cid]))
29     prioritized.append(remaining.pop(first_id))
30
31     while remaining:
32         # current average vector of prioritized configs
33         P = np.stack([vecs[cfg.id] for cfg in prioritized], axis=0)
34         avg_vec = P.mean(axis=0)
35
36         # compute distances from avg_vec
37         ids = list(remaining.keys())
38         dists = []
39         for cid in ids:
40             v = vecs[cid]
41             d = np.linalg.norm(v - avg_vec)
42             dists.append((cid, d))
43
44         # sort by distance descending: farthest (most diverse) first
45         dists.sort(key=lambda x: x[1], reverse=True)
46         # choose top-k as candidates
47         candidates = [cid for (cid, _) in dists[:k_candidates]]
48
49         # among candidates, choose lowest estimated energy
```

```

49     best_id = min(candidates, key=lambda cid: estimate_energy_score(remaining[cid
    ]))
50     prioritized.append(remaining.pop(best_id))
51
52     return prioritized

```

The logic does not attempt to replicate the original GREEDY_E implementation exactly. Instead, it preserves the main principle: prioritize tests that are both informative (diverse) and relatively inexpensive, so that early execution achieves a better energy-per-confidence profile.

E.4 Selective Regression Test Selection

For the maintenance phase, a lightweight selective regression mechanism was implemented on top of Git change detection. Instead of running the entire test suite after every modification, the system identifies changed files and maps them to impacted tests through an explicit dependency map.

Listing E.4 shows the essential logic.

Listing E.4. Selective regression test selection based on changed files.

```

1 IMPACT_MAP = {
2     "refactored/core/gaussian.py": [
3         "refactored/tests/unit/test_gaussian.py",
4         "refactored/tests/integration/test_pipeline_stages.py",
5     ],
6     "refactored/core/sobel.py": [
7         "refactored/tests/unit/test_sobel_and_mag.py",
8         "refactored/tests/integration/test_pipeline_stages.py",
9     ],
10    "refactored/core/grayscale.py": [
11        "refactored/tests/unit/test_grayscale.py",
12        "refactored/tests/integration/test_pipeline_stages.py",
13    ],
14 }
15
16 def impacted_tests_from_files(changed_files: List[str]) -> List[str]:
17     tests = set()
18     for f in changed_files:
19         for key_suffix, mapped_tests in IMPACT_MAP.items():
20             if f.endswith(key_suffix):
21                 tests.update(mapped_tests)
22     return sorted(tests)
23
24 changed = get_changed_files("HEAD~1")
25 impacted = impacted_tests_from_files(changed)
26 cmd = ["pytest", "-q", *impacted]

```

This selective runner was intentionally designed as a transparent and reproducible alternative to heavyweight industrial build systems. Its role in the thesis is not to introduce a new regression-testing algorithm, but to demonstrate how architectural modularization enables proportional

maintenance effort.

E.5 Maintenance Artifact Generation

To make maintenance events reproducible and auditable, each selective run was recorded as a structured JSON artifact. Listing E.5 shows the core reporting logic.

Listing E.5. Generation of JSON maintenance artifacts.

```
1 report = {
2     "timestamp_utc": datetime.utcnow().isoformat(),
3     "base": base,
4     "repo_root": repo_root(),
5     "changed_files": changed_files,
6     "impacted_tests": impacted,
7     "pytest_cmd": cmd,
8 }
9
10 with open(json_path, "w", encoding="utf-8") as f:
11     json.dump(report, f, indent=2)
```

These artifacts were used in the maintenance evaluation to show which source changes triggered which tests, thereby providing evidence that the refactored architecture supports proportional regression testing.

Appendix F

Repository Structure

This appendix provides an overview of the repository structure used for the experimental implementation after the design comparison in the thesis which uses Strategy-based Data-Oriented Architecture as the baseline. The project was initially implemented as a single prototype pipeline for each architecture across different programming languages together with image inputs. During the research process after the design comparison - the data-oriented pipeline was chosen to be the preferred approach, the system was gradually reorganized into modular components that separate the core image-processing logic, testing infrastructure, experimental execution scripts, and result analysis tools.

This modular organization improves readability, simplifies maintenance, and ensures reproducibility of the experiments presented in this thesis. The repository therefore reflects the different phases of the software lifecycle investigated in this work, including development, testing, deployment, and maintenance experiments.

The overall organization of the repository used for implementing the experimental pipelines and evaluation framework is shown in the Figure F.1.

Figure F.1. Directory structure of the experimental project used in this thesis.

The project started with the implementation of the initial pipelines in different architectural styles, in a singular file such as `strategy_soa_pipeline.py` alongside an input directory for the input dataset. The outputs of the design comparison for each architecture was stored in the `results.<architecture name>` directory with configurations as each step name. Later, as described above, Strategy based pipeline was cAs the project evolved, the core image-processing logic was refactored into separate modules within the `core` directory.

The `core` directory contains the fundamental image-processing operations used across all architectural implementations. These modules implement the main processing stages of the pipeline, including grayscale conversion, Gaussian blur filtering, Sobel edge detection, magnitude calculation, and input/output utilities.

Testing infrastructure is located in two directories one `tests` for storing the actual tests and later on a different directory `testing_infrastructure` was created as a separate directory inside the root directory to store the execution runners are provided to automate the execution of unit tests, integration tests, and end-to-end grid evaluations including the $GREEDY_E$ prioritization. The `tests` directory contains unit tests validating individual processing components as well as integration tests verifying correct interaction between pipeline stages.

The directory `comparison_and_plotting` contains scripts responsible for analyzing experimental outputs and generating visualizations used in the evaluation chapters. These scripts aggregate raw execution logs, compute derived metrics such as energy consumption and runtime comparisons, and produce figures that summarize the results of deployment, maintenance, and end-to-end experiments.

The `images` directory stores the input images used as datasets for the image-processing pipeline experiments. This organization allows experimental scripts, testing infrastructure, and analysis utilities to interact with a shared processing implementation while keeping responsibilities clearly separated. This organization allows experimental scripts, testing infrastructure, and analysis utilities to interact with a shared processing implementation while keeping responsibilities clearly separated.